

Project 539369-LLP-1-2013-1-ES-ERASMUS-ENW

Start: 1.10.2013

Duration: 36 months

Funded with the support from the European Commission.

OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Deliverable 2.4

Research Matrix – Mapping research within the network

Revision: 3

Due date: 2016-09-30 (m36)

Lead partner: UCLan

Deliverable Administration and Summary

No & name	D2.4 Research Matrix – Mapping research within the network				
Status	Final	Due	M36 (2016-09-30)	Final version	2017-02-28
Author(s)	Karim Hadjri (UCLan)				
Editor					
Work Programme Description	This deliverable was produced following the need to map existing research initially within the subnetwork research then within OIKONET in order to identify key research themes, output, references and expertise that can benefit the network as a whole. This also helped in identifying potential synergies between the three subnetworks. This exercise was so successful that the team felt it deserves to be added as a deliverable.				
Comments	A previous version of this document was submitted along with the interim report in April 2015.				

Document history

V	Date	Author	Description
1	2015-04-19	Karim Hadjri (UCLan)	Document structure and matrix details and content
2	2016-06-30	Karim Hadjri (UCLan)	Document structure and revised matrix details and content
3	2016-10-24	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Final editing

Table of Contents

1 Executive Summary	4
2 Introduction	5
2.1 Purpose and target group.....	5
2.2 Contribution of partners	5
2.3 Relations to other activities in the project.....	6
3 Mapping research themes	7
4 Mapping research themes to outputs	9
5 Appendix A: Matrix 1: Mapping research themes	11
6 Appendix B: Matrix 2: Mapping research themes to outputs	19
7 Appendix C: Bibliography	22
7.1 Urban Regeneration	22
7.2 Energy	23
7.3 Indoor air quality.....	24
7.4 Mobility.....	27
7.5 Wayfinding.....	28
7.6 Urban climate	29
7.7 Cooling and heating	32
7.8 Waterfront	33

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The research activity at the partner organisations have been mapped and collected in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of OIKONET. A first matrix was created to record existing research and potential synergies on three themes: Sustainability, Design and Participation. For each of the three themes, drivers, barriers, indicators, methods, case studies, and bibliography were provided by partners. This matrix is included in Appendix A. In the last stage of the project, a second matrix was produced to map the research themes to the project outputs. This second matrix is included in Appendix B. A list of references provided by partners with regard to their areas of research is included in Appendix C.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

The purpose of the matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of the OIKONET project. This matrix can be useful to OIKONET partners and to third parties to inform research, teaching, practice, policy or user engagement in learning and research activities related to the study of contemporary housing issues. In particular, it presents relevant projects and initiatives undertaken by the partners on housing topics concerned with sustainability, design and participation.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The sub-network Housing Research is led by UCLan who are responsible for the research aspects of the network.

25 partners provided inputs for the first version of the research matrix:

- P1 LA SALLE- School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain
- P2 ETSA-UPV- School of Architecture of Valencia, Spain
- P3 FASTU- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, Bratislava, Slovakia
- P4 KUL- Faculty of Architecture, KU Leuven, Gent/Brussels, Belgium
- P7 CHALMERS - University of Chalmers, Sweden
- P8 IHS- Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, The Netherlands
- P10 UKIM – Faculty of Architecture, University Ss. Cyril and Methodius, Macedonia
- P11 OAPPCR- Ordine degli Architetti, Pianificatori, Paesaggisti e Conservatori della Provincia di Rimini Italy
- P12 UL- Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
- P13 AAU- School of Architecture, Design and Planning, Aalborg University, Denmark
- P14 RTU - Faculty of Architecture and Urban Planning at Riga Technical University, Latvia
- P15 UCY- Faculty of Architecture, University of Cyprus, Cyprus
- P16 UCLAN- Grenfell-Baines Institute of Architecture, University of Central Lancashire, UK
- P17 PFZ- Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia
- P19 NOVA- Norwegian Social Research, Norway
- P21 SOSTRE CIVIC, Sostre Cívic, Spain
- P22 POLIS- Polis University, Albania
- P23 HERISCAPE- Heriscape, Italy
- P24 BRATISLAVA, City of Bratislava, Slovakia
- P25 ISCTE-IUL University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal

- P26 AF BELGRADE- Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
- P28 ELTE- Faculty of Social Sciences, Eötvös Loránd University, Hungary
- P31 VSUACE-Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Russia
- P32 FAU- Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo, Universidad de Chile
- P34 UN Habitat, Kenya

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The work produced by this subnetwork is informing the activities conducted by the subnetworks Community Participation (WP3) and Pedagogical Activities (WP4). The research matrix that was collaboratively produced with the contributions from partners of these subnetworks. The relationships between research themes and project outputs have been introduced in the visual graph developed in WP5 Digital Platform and it is available in Oikotnetwork at the project website.

3 MAPPING RESEARCH THEMES

In order to map existing research and identify potential synergies between partners across the three sub-networks – Housing Research, Community Participation and Pedagogical Activities–, a research matrix was created. With this purpose, a matrix structured in three themes was created to collect from partners (Figure 1):

- **SUSTAINABILITY.** Mainstream sustainability is framed around three dimensions: Environmental, Social and Economics. Environmental includes a viable natural and built environment and also covers Sustainable Design. Social includes nurturing community and an equitable social environment. Economics refers to sufficient economy, sustainable economic development, and sustainable development. Sustainable development is the aim of the interrelation between the three dimensions. Partners were asked to highlight any of these aspects of sustainability they are engaged with.
- **DESIGN.** Housing design is a crucial aspect of the OIKONET project as highlighted by the various pedagogic and participatory activities. This includes an understanding through research of design methods, concepts, and applications including computing in Architecture and Spatial Planning. This is particularly useful to partners from the sub-network Pedagogical Activities.
- **PARTICIPATION.** Participation is one of the drivers of the OIKONET project and is covered by WP3 Community Participation. The matrix sought to collect existing research and user engagement capacity within the network so that whole network could benefit from this knowledge.

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX		CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH				SUBNETWORK WP2		21/09/2014	
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Headings (h3) and the Oikopedia entries (h3).</p>									
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand the research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	WP3 PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.
SUSTAINABILITY (Environmental, Social, Economic)									
Mainstream sustainability thinking is framed around three dimensions: environmental, social and economic sustainability. Environmental includes a viable natural and built environment and also covers Sustainable Design. Social includes nurturing community and an equitable social environment. Economic refers to sufficient economy, sustainable economic development, and sustainable development. Sustainable development is the aim of the interrelation between the three dimensions.									
Environmental sustainability									
Energy	High energy costs: health and wellbeing.	Expensive alternatives (solar, wind, geothermal).	Reducing energy consumption and CO2 emissions. Healthy buildings.	Energy consumption measurements. UK Code for Sustainable Homes.	British Research Establishment Science Park (Kingspan).	See Energy sources Sheet.	FASTU: 1. Seminar on Low energy houses. Bc. 2. Seminar on Alternative technologies. ING, both winter term.	SostreCivc : Low energy building rehabilitation. Centralized energy systems.	UCLan, La Salle, FASTU, SOSTRECIVIC
Indoor air quality (IAQ)	High energy costs: health and wellbeing of elderly people	Increased air tightness to reduce energy costs and CO2 emissions. old elderly home buildings without contemporary buildings service systems	Reducing energy consumption and CO2 emissions. Healthy buildings: building service systems performance indicators (COP), reduced energy consumption	Indoor air quality measurements, physical measurements and survey among residents	British Research Establishment Science Park (Kingspan), typical elderly homes.	See IAQ sources Sheet. See Sources sheet 'Energy'	FASTU: Seminar on Environmentally friendly architecture. Bc, winter term		UCLan, FASTU
Energy (toward nZEB)	planning buildings toward nZEB	lack of professional knowledge	professionals response	upgrading computational tool developed for energy labeling to enable instant analysing of cost optimality measures	computational tool for energy labeling that is already in use on national level will be extended in two levels: a) for analysing of cost optimal measures of improving building envelope properties and b) for analysing of building integrated technologies for decentralised production of heat and electricity	See Sources sheet 'Energy'	FASTU: 1. Design studio in Module: Architecture and ecology. Bc, winter term; 2. Design studio on Experimental and ecology determined design. ING, summer term		UL, La Salle, FASTU
Urban planning	reducing of urban and street heat island, improving outdoor and indoor environment	lack of professional knowledge, additional costs of building constructions	thermal comfort parameters, air pollution indicators, thermal response of green roof building constructions	experiments on different green roof constructions including measurements of thermal response, water accumulation and cooling of ambient air above green roof constructions	in-situ experiments	See Sources sheet 'Energy'	FASTU: Seminar on Sustainable urban development. ING, winter term		UL, La Salle, FASTU
Energy (improving free cooling and heating)	reducing of energy demand of buildings for heating and cooling	possible additional costs in case of not optimal operation	building service systems performance indicators (COP), reduced energy consumption	developing of operation optimisation algorithms of free cooling and free heating systems based on numerical modelling including weather forecasting and future thermal response of buildings	in-situ experiments	See Sources sheet 'Energy'			UL

Figure 1. First matrix: mapping research activity in the network

Partners were expected to fill in the matrix, answering to the following questions:

1. **Key research issues:** What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?
2. **Drivers:** What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?
3. **Barriers:** What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?
4. **Indicators:** What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?
5. **Methods:** What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?
6. **Case studies:** What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?
7. **Sources:** What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?
8. **PEDAGOGY:** WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research issue.
9. **PARTICIPATION:** WP3 PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.
10. **PARTNERS:** ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.

4 MAPPING RESEARCH THEMES TO OUTPUTS

During the third and final year of the project the team revised the research matrix to align it with actual project outputs, namely: (1) the Readers, Oikopedia entries and the Book; (2) pedagogic activities; and (3) participatory activities.

The new matrix was structured in four research themes:

- SUSTAINABILITY
- PARTICIPATION
- AFFORDABLE HOUSING
- HOUSING REGENERATION

Each theme has a number of research issues which are briefly described and mapped onto the various outputs and activities. This provides a clear idea of where a certain topic is examined and what output have been generated during the course of the project life (Figure 2).

OIKONET REVISED RESEARCH MATRIX		V2	SUBNETWORK WP2	30/06/2016			
The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activities that have informed OIKONET (research, pedagogy, participation) and have led to a particular academic publication.							
Research concept	Description	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	OIKOPEDIA	Reader 1	Reader 2	Other publication
The research concepts that have emerged as critical and necessary to understand the global dimension of housing.	A brief description of the research concept or theme.	Pedagogic activities that have been informed by this concept.	Participation activities that have been informed by this concept.	OIKOPEDIA entries connected to this concept.	Sections in Reader 1 that have covered this concept.	Sections in Reader 2 that have covered this concept.	Other publications that related to this concept and its link to OIKONET activities.
Sustainability							
Sustainable or green building construction of housing	It endorses the principals of sustainable development in the siting, design, building, maintenance and occupation of buildings.			Urban greening Urban heat islands mitigation		Chapter 2	World Renewable Energy Congress WREC XIV paper
Energy efficiency in housing	Is concerned with energy performance and is one key aspect influenced by design and cuts across several facets of the society such as social, economic and environmental.			Passive Design (RTU)	Chapter 3	Chapter 5	
Sustainable housing design	Conserve energy, reduce the waste generation and be environmentally equitable.			Sustainable Design. Sustainable Design - learning by doing.	Chapter 1		
Socially sustainable transformation of communities and cities	Maintaining social cohesion and ensuring citizens participation during and after urban transformations.	Learning space "Urban Systems"		Sustainable Communities, Capacity-building, Interplace, Codesign	Chapter 2	Chapter 7, Chapter 3	
Economic sustainability	Creating affordable or social housing projects that are economically sustainable in the long term. This means the ability to support or continue indefinitely, without economic repercussions.			Sustainable Communities; Housing innovations; Public Rental Housing Programme as Innovation - Brief	Chapter 6	Chapter 6	
Participation							
Community, users or citizens' participation	Aims at taking into account inhabitants' requirements in housing design and planning.	Learning space "Civic Housing"	Participatory action "Civic Housing"	Participatory Planning (RTU), Capacity-building, Interplace, Codesign	Chapter 2	Chapter 7, Chapter 3, Chapter 6 (IHS, RTU)	
Citizens' empowerment	Inhabitants are key actors in governance processes aimed at developing the city.			Capacity-building, Interplace, Codesign	Chapter 2	Chapter 7	

Figure 2. Second matrix: mapping research themes to project outputs

The information contained in this second matrix includes:

- **Research concept:** The research concepts that have emerged as critical and necessary to understand the global dimension of housing.
- **Description:** A brief description of the research concept or theme.
- **PEDAGOGY:** Pedagogic activities that have been informed by this concept.
- **PARTICIPATION:** Participation activities that have been informed by this concept.
- **OIKOPEDIA:** entries connected to this concept.
- **READER 1:** sections that have covered this concept.
- **READER 2:** sections that have covered this concept.
- **Other publications:** related to this concept and the link to OIKONET activities.

The contents of the second matrix have been introduced in Oikonetwork to facilitate the access to the project outputs by navigating through the network of research themes and issues.

Figure 3. Visualization of the matrix in Oikonetwork

5 APPENDIX A: MATRIX 1: MAPPING RESEARCH THEMES

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH							SUBNETWORK WP2	21/09/2014	
The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Readings (x3) and the Oikopedia entries (x3).									
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	WP3 PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	ALL PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution.
SUSTAINABILITY (Environmental, Social, Economic)									
Mainstream sustainability thinking is framed around three dimensions: environmental, social and economic sustainability. Environmental includes a viable natural and built environment and also covers Sustainable Design. Social includes nurturing community and an equitable social environment. Economic refers to sufficient economy, sustainable economic development, and sustainable development. Sustainable development is the aim of the interrelation between the three dimensions.									
Environmental sustainability									
Energy	High energy costs; health and wellbeing.	Expensive alternatives (solar, wind, geothermal).	Reducing energy consumption and CO2 emissions. Healthy buildings.	Energy consumption measurements. UK Code for Sustainable Homes.	British Research Establishment Science Park (Kingspan).	See Energy sources Sheet.	FASTU: 1. Seminar on Low energy houses, Bc; 2. Seminar on Alternative technologies, ING, both winter term	SostreCivic : Low energy building rehabilitation. Centralized energy systems.	UCLan, La Salle, FASTU, SOSTRECIVIC
Indoor air quality (IAQ)	High energy costs; health and wellbeing of elderly people	Increased air tightness to reduce energy costs and CO2 emissions. old elderly home buildings without contemporary buildings service systems	Reducing energy consumption and CO2 emissions. Healthy buildings. building service systems performance indicators (COP), reduced energy consumption	Indoor air quality measurements. physical measurements and survey among residents	British Research Establishment Science Park (Kingspan). typical elderly homes.	See IAQ sources Sheet. See Sources sheet 'Energy'	FASTU: Seminar on Environmentally friendly architecture, Bc, winter term		UCLan, FASTU
Energy (toward nZEB)	planning buildings toward nZEB	lack of professional knowledge	professionals response	upgrading computational tool developed for energy labeling to enable instant analysing of cost optimally measures	computational tool for energy labeling that is already in use on national level will be extended in two levels: a) for analysing of cost optimal measures of improving building envelope properties and b) for analysing of building integrated technologies for decentralised production of heat and electricity	See Sources sheet 'Energy'	FASTU: 1. Design studio in Module: Architecture and ecology, Bc, winter term; 2. Design studio on Experimental and ecology determined design, ING, summer term		UL, La Salle, FASTU
Urban planning	reducing of urban and street heat island, improving outdoor and indoor environment	lack of professional knowledge, additional costs of building constructions	thermal comfort parameters, air pollution indicators, thermal of response of green roof building constructions	experiments on different green roof constructions including measurements of thermal response, water accumulation and cooling of ambient air above green roof constructions	in-situ experiments	See Sources sheet 'Energy'	FASTU: Seminar on Sustainable urban development, ING, winter term		UL, La Salle, FASTU
Energy (improving free cooling and heating)	reducing of energy demand of buildings for heating and cooling	possible additional costs in case of not optimal operation	building service systems performance indicators (COP), reduced energy consumption	developing of operation optimisation algorithms of free cooling and free heating systems based on numerical modelling including weather forecasting and future thermal response of buildings	in-situ experiments	See Sources sheet 'Energy'			UL

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX		CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH					SUBNETWORK WP2	21/09/2014		
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Readings (x3) and the Oikopedia entries (x3).</p>										
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS	
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	WP3 PARTNERS-Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.	
Energy (improving free cooling and heating)	reducing of energy demand of buildings for heating and cooling	possible additional costs in case of not optimal operation	building service systems performance indicators (COP), reduced energy consumption	improving efficiency of heating and cooling with thermal activated constructions (TABs) by combining panel heating/cooling with mechanical ventilation systems	laboratory experiments, in-situ experiments, numerical modelling	See Sources sheet 'Energy'			UL	
Social sustainability										
Public rental housing as social innovation	to recognise added value of the programme	partnership with city of Zagreb	Interes of other cities to implement such programme	Face to face survey using questionnaire	Some typical households from the programme	Housing innovations, housing in transitional countries	UPMF-IUG postgraduate course on Sustainable planning and housing	SostreCivic : new models to housing access and participation	ISP, SOSTRECIVIC	
Welfare and housing	Exploring the opportunities for improving housing conditions and welfare for vulnerable households	Lack of sufficient funds, wicked problems - no quick fixes available	Housing outcomes as compared to the hypothetical contrafactual situation without any interventions	Eclectic and diverse	National databases, local studies in municipalities etc..	Collaboration with policy makers and administrators. Literature on effects of housing market interventions.	UPMF-IUG postgraduate course on Sustainable planning and housing	P23-Heriscapè, P11-Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini: RIMINI- Case study / SostreCivic : tools to avoid energy poverty	NOVA	
Housing, social inequality and the life course	Improved understanding of social inequality and the role of housing, e.g. tenure and timing of family formation	Inequality may be a societal problem. Remedies are not obvious, but the need to look for remedies are obvious	Mapping of inequalities, e.g. using Gini's. Identifying drivers of changing inequality. Conflicts/disparities between cohorts.	Dynamic analyses of housing market outcomes. Identifying components of dynamic autocorrelation. Regression discontinuities, IV regression	Life courses of different cohorts. Tenure choice over time	Register data, house price statistics, EU-silc, etc		SostreCivic : mapping empty houses in towns and design tools to activate it.	NOVA, SOSTRECIVIC	
Socially sustainable transformation of cities	Provides knowledge for novel models of transformation and innovative residential typologies	Communication with local residents and negotiating the existing urban plans	Development of productive partnership with local residents and local authorities	Survey among the residents, citizens participation, interactive visualisation tools, development and evaluation of new scenarios	Development of Urban boulevard in Skopje	Urban transformation and citizens participation literature	UKIM: Integrative design studio (Fall semester). UCLan: MArch Landscape Futures design studio (high-density housing).	P22-Regulatory Plan of the City of Burrel, Albania	UKIM, UCLAN, U-POLIS	
Economic sustainability										
Urban dynamics	Provide a knowledge base for planning at local levels	Spatial disparities	segregation measures over time, price dispersion, drivers of mobility	Statistical analyses, accounting for spatial dependencies, survival analyses, discontinuities	Oslo, Haugesund and surrounding municipalities - Budapest and suburban area	Statistical analyses of register data and own data collection (See Sources sheet 'Segregation')			NOVA, ELTE, La Salle	

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX							CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH			SUBNETWORK WP2	21/09/2014
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Readings (x3) and the Oikopedia entries (x3).</p>											
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS		
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	WP3 PARTNERS- Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.		
Affordable housing	Lack of sustainable affordable housing worldwide	Priorization of economic sustainability the over other dimensions of sustainability: environmental, cultural and social	Carbon credits, energy emissions, socio-cultural needs and requirements, employment through green housing	Literature reviews, pilot programmes, assessments	UN-Habitat field programmes related to green housing	Sustainable Housing for Sustainable Cities: A Policy Guide for Developing Countries (2012), http://www.unhabitat.org/pmss/listItemDetails.aspx?publicationID=3365 and Going Green: A Handbook of Sustainable Housing Practices in Developing Countries (2012), http://www.unhabitat.org/pmss/listItemDetails.aspx?publicationID=3364 .	UN-Habitat, Global Network for Sustainable Housing (GNSH)		UN-Habitat		
Families in mortgage crisis	A new, rapidly growing crisis-group emerged lately the households unable to pay their mortgage instalments and threatened by losing their home. In spite of the great deal of interest we see a lack of systematic analysis of the residential mortgage problems	lack of data on mortgage problems of Banks. No interests in social-housing agency	To give more structural picture of the mortgage crisis on macro (policy) and micro (household) level combined with spatial inequalities. Answer the question whether the social-housing agency could be one solution.	both qualitative (interviews and focus group) and quantitative studies (questionnaires)	Tenure and renter choice over time. Life courses of different cohorts.	Literature on housing policy, housing preferences and mortgage crisis. (See Sources sheet 'Mortgage')			ELTE		
DESIGN (Methods, Concepts, Applications in Architecture and Spatial Planning)											
Design Methods											
Residential segregation	exploring the relationship between urban residential segregation and social exclusion	lack of unifying spatial framework in urban segregation research	socio-spatial segregation measures through time and mapping of a number of variables - GIS	both quantitative (spatial analysis) and qualitative (ethnography, observations, questionnaires)	local municipalities, urban centres in Cyprus - Budapest and particularly the inner city area	Urban segregation literature (See Sources sheet 'Segregation')	UCY- postgraduate course on urban segregation - each fall semester / ETSAV_postgraduate course on architecture- each fall semester. THRESHOLD MATTERS workspace		UCY, ELTE, ETSAV		
Domestic Space Organisation	Need to explore and research ways of expression and incorporation of cultural/social characteristics in domestic space, utilizing architectural methods and tools	need of field studies for a long period of time	results are varied - both from qualitative (observations/questionnaires/visual ethnography) and quantitative studies (measurable spatial analysis, statistical analysis and correlations)	both qualitative (observations/questionnaires/visual ethnography) and quantitative studies (measurable spatial analysis, statistical analysis and correlations)	case studies of a big sample of houses in Cyprus	domestic space organisation literature	ETSAV_postgraduate course on architecture- each fall semester. THRESHOLD MATTERS workspace / UCY - design studio on domestic space	SostreCivic : design studio on domestic spaces rehabilitation	UCY, ETSAV, SOSTRECIVIC		
The section as a design tool	Space is inherent in a plan but visual in a section. The power of the section as a design tool is not fully understood by students (and architects)			Design assignment	Architectural projects	Architectural projects	KUL: OIKONET elective		KUL		

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX		CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH					SUBNETWORK WP2		21/09/2014
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Readings (x3) and the Oikopedia entries (x3).</p>									
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	WP3 PARTNERS-Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.
Parametric Urban Design	Exploring the potential for parametric design as a communication tool for collaborative urban design	Need for tool development	User feedback from relevant user groups	1) developing, 2) testing, and 3) evaluating parametric design tools	participatory design workshops in collaboration with municipal planning offices	Literature on 1) parametric design, 2) urban design, and 3) participatory design processes	AAU: Urban design and site design course at BSc4 level: Sub-themes: 1) New forms of co-creation: Building associations (Baugruppen). 2) The car-free city (when the Google-car turns cars from products into services).		AAU
Design Concepts									
Mobility	Ageing population.	Expensive retrofitting of a massive old housing stock.	Meeting UK Lifetime Home standards.	User feedback.	UK Lifetime Homes standards.	See Mobility sources Sheet.			UCLan
Wayfinding	People with dementia.	Lack of design guidelines.	Walks with people with dementia.	Observation and feedback from carers.	Dementia Development Services Centre (DSDC).	See Wayfinding sources Sheet.			UCLan
Sustainable renovation	Need for refurbishment of 850.000 apartments from the 'million program' within ten years.	Lack of economic resources for renovation. Gentrification harm society. Lack of positive experience of how to involve tenants.	See above.	Living lab.	Chalmers is involved in research in a new Renovation Centre in Sweden, with a living lab in Hammarkullen. Gothenburg. RTU: involved in research about large-scale housing areas in Riga	See Wayfinding sources Sheet.	1. ISTAR, VitruviusFABLAB, ISCTE-IUL, Alexandra Paio. 2. FAVSUACE - project courses for the 3rd year students "Multi-storey residential building - complex", "Residential area", "Reconstruction of the quarter". 3. FASTU: Seminar on housing revitalization, ING, summer term. 4. ETSAV_postgraduate course on architecture-each fall semester. THRESHOLD MATTERS workspace. 5. RTU: Master student's thesis, seminars; student's workshops together with Riga City Architect's Office	SostreCivic : Case study	Chalmers, ISCTE, FASTU, FAVSUACE, ETSAV, SOSTRECIVIC, RTU
Sustainable Inner cities	Need comparative studies of recent social processes in CEE, focusing on social sustainability and gentrification, participation, and the potential social conflicts emerging in this area.	Lack of economic resources for renovation. Increasing social conflicts.	Following the process of urban renewal and participatory processes. Mapping the social and urbanistic results. Mapping the forced migration.	Both qualitative (interviews and focus group) and quantitative studies (questioners)	Budapest inner city area				ELTE
Public-Private Interface	The underestimation of the impact of the quality of the private dwelling to the public space and the importance of a mediating between the two.			Design assignment	Recent architectural projects (Moriyama House, House N,...)	see sources	KUL OIKONET-Elective Threshold Matter		KUL

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX		CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH					SUBNETWORK WP2		21/09/2014
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Readings (x3) and the Oikopedia entries (x3).</p>									
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research Issue.	WP3 PARTNERS-Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research Issue.	ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.
Design Applications									
Urban Design of Waterfront Regeneration	Existing local initiatives from public, private and civil sectors in waterfront area	Lack of knowledge of the potentialities of integrative urban design process in waterfront regeneration	Level and type of integrated visions and strategies for waterfront regeneration	Integrative urban design game (new method inovated by Tatjana Mrdenović, that integrates various ones regards disciplinary, interdisciplinarity, collaboration, art, logic, social knowledge, positivistic knowledge)	Savamala district in Belgrade as a poligon for integrating differences (visions, view points, interests, needs) into coherent unity through worksops, trainings, on the field interviews, round tables, discussions, presentations	See Waterfront Sheet	AF_BELGRADE. Teaching Course: Integrative Urban Design of Savamala	P23-Heriscape	AF BELGRADE, HERISCAPE
Compact Cities	Sustainable development missions. Urbanization processes. Increasing economic inequalities.	Lack of knowledge concerning pros and cons with compact cities. Economic crisis - lack of resources for construction. Lack of political action. Lack of dialogue with citizens criticizing densification of their neighbourhoods.	See above.	See above.	We are involved in research with case studies in Barcelona, Rotterdam and Gothenburg.	See Wayfinding sources Sheet.	1. ISTAR, VitruviusFABLAB, ISCTE-IUL, Alexandra Paio. 2. UPMF - IUG Postgraduate design studio on densification strategies 3. FAVSUACE - lecture courses for the 5th year students "Ecological basis of territorial planning and urban design", "The architectural and landscape complexes" and project courses "City", "Reconstruction of the city". 4. FASTU: Specialized CAD studio-verification of the planned highrise buildings in the (compact) city veduta; cooperation with BA municipality, Bc, winter term	P23-Heriscape	CHALMERS, HERISCAPE, FAVSUACE, FASTU, ISCTE
PARTICIPATION									
Involving children in urban design and planning	The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. Followed by Municipal document on the same topic.	Uncertainty about how representative democracy is influenced by children's participation.	We carry out qualitative studies where the results are multifaceted. Results are often discussed in collaboration between researchers and practitioners.	Interviews, participant observation, workshops, case studies.	We are involved in research related to a place called Hammarkullen in Gothenburg, Sweden.	See Wayfinding sources Sheet.	ISTAR, VitruviusFABLAB, ISCTE-IUL, Alexandra Paio / TSA Valencia design course second year_workspace Introduction to housing		CHALMERS, ISCTE, ETSAV

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX		CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH					SUBNETWORK WP2		21/09/2014
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Readings (x3) and the Oikopedia entries (x3).</p>									
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	WP3 PARTNERS- Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.
Place making and codesign	Declining electoral participation and changes in the political structures of society entails a need for new ways of citizen participation in urban development, as society degenerates without commitment.	Lack of economic resources and positive experience of how to involve citizens and inhabitants in different kinds of processes. Professionals of different kinds need to develop new approaches to citizens and social movements need to adapt to planning processes, to not be left behind and without influence - just protesting is not enough any more.	See above.	Interviews, participant observation, workshops, case studies.	We are involved in research trying to learn from how citizens and planners in Cuba act on these issues. We will hopefully also develop a new research project soon, learning from how the municipalities of Malmö and Gothenburg relate to social movements aimed at citizen influence on urban design.	See Wayfinding sources Sheet.	1. ISTAR, VitruviusFABLAB, ISCTE-IUL, Alexandra Paio. 2. BUT - Intro to urban design 3. FA STU: Specialized CAD studio- designing waterfront public spaces in the residential district, citizens participation 4. .ETSA Valencia_ design course second year_ workspace Introduction to housing	BA City: application of participative actions, cooperation with pedagogy, outputs for the urban planning process. P23-Heriscape, P11- Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini: RIMINI- Case study	Chelmers, La Salle, Bratislava, HERISCAPE, ORDINE, ETSAV, SOSTRECIVIC
Resettlement	The number of people affected by resettlement is increasing, increasingly through new models of resettlement with private sector involvement, while not sure what the impact is on relocatees.	Neo liberal paradigm in India, governments seek to reduce costs through private sector involvement (new governance) and externalisation of impact on relocatees	Measure the impact on upward mobility through quasi experiment and life histories, comparing different models	Qualitative (life histories, in-depth interviews, FGD) and quantitative (quasi experiment, survey through questionnaires)	Still working on	See resettlement sheet			IHS
Community participation workshop	Exploring the tools for negotiation of the proces of urban development with local residents and authorities	Lack of interest in citizens participation and cooperation with local authorities	Design of new public spaces in cooperation with local residents	Intreviews, data collection, mapping and workshops with citizens	Local municipalities in Skopje	Urban transformation and citizens participation literature	LA SALLE In the elective seminar "Civic Housing" we have carried out a co-design exercise with members of SostreCivic. We plan to do a similar collaboration with Heriscape in a case study in Rimini, being prepared within WP3 / ETSAV_ postgraduate course on architecture- each fall semester_ THRESHOLD MATTERS workspace		UKIM, La Salle, ETSAV, SOSTRECIVIC
Communication tools	The lack of understanding between professionals and non-professional in relation with housing and urban issues.	Requires the involvement of another disciplines such as sociology, environmental psychology and anthropology.	Results on participation workshops and activities.	Experimental methodologies	We are involved in a Case study in Barcelona designing participatory processes for the inclusion of dwellers into the design process of their future flats	See Wayfinding sources Sheet.	La Salle- In the elective seminar on Housing Research, takes place in the Fall semester		La Salle
Integrative urban design in urban regeneration	Existing local initiatives from public, private and civil sectors that need to be integrated	Lack of knowledge of the potentialities of integrative participatory process and integrative urban design	Level and type of participation	Integrative urban design game (new method inovated by Tatjana Mrdenovic, that integrates various ones regards disciplinarity, interdisciplinarity, collaboration, art, logic, social knowledge, positivistic knowledge)	Savamala district in Belgrade as a polligon for integrating differences (visions, view points, interests, needs) into coherent unity through workshops, trainings, on the field interviews, round tables, discussions, presentations	See Urban Regen Sheet	AF_BELGRADE Teaching course: Savamala Incubator - Integrative Urban Design in Savamala regeneration. The main goal of the research is to test various methods of participation in the reality using art and creativity to ovecome differences. http://www.arh.bg.ac.rs/?portfolio=kurs-23-2-strucna-ekskurzija-ill-radionica	BA - City: cooperation and integration of the methodology to the participative process in Bratislava case study. P23-Heriscape, P11- Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini: RIMINI- Case study / BRATISLAVA Renovation of public spaces	AF_BELGRADE, BRATISLAVA, HERISCAPE, ORDINE

OIKONET RESEARCH MATRIX		CONTEMPORARY HOUSING RESEARCH					SUBNETWORK WP2	21/09/2014	
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activity at partner organisations in order to enable knowledge exchange and collaboration in line with the aims and objectives of Oikonet. Small working groups will be set up according to the three themes listed below. This will allow for effective development of the project's deliverables namely the Readings (x3) and the Oikopedia entries (x3).</p>									
Key research issues	Drivers	Barriers	Indicators	Methods	Case studies	Sources	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	PARTNERS
What are the main research issues you are currently studying under the 3 headings below?	What are the main drivers behind the need to conduct research on these specific issues?	What are the main barriers that are or will prevent achieving targets and resolving issues?	What indicators and/or metrics will be used to measure the effects and benefits of your proposals/solutions?	What research methods you are using or will use to answer or resolve your key research issues?	What key case studies you think can be examined to inform this research?	What key sources and publications you suggest are important to further understand this research issues?	WP4 PEDAGOGY PARTNERS. Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your pedagogic activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	WP3 PARTNERS-Please insert the acronym of your institution and the title of your community participation activity in the corresponding Key research issue.	ALL PARTNERS: Please insert the acronym of your institution.
Private and public collaboration	Exploring existing initiatives on Social Housing from NGOs and private promoters into coordinate actions with public authorities	Lack of Knowledge and coordination among all actors (private and public)	Level and type of integrated actions to promote social housing	Data collections, mapping, interviews, and work-table	Rimini	Reports from public authorities, economic associations and NGO.		P23-Heriscapè, P11-Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini: RIMINI- Case study / SostreCivic : Private cooperative rehabilitation through a surface right of public building	HERISCAPE, ORDINE, SOSTRECIVIC
Participatory planning in local urban management	the main objective of the research is to identify the key factors for developing an effective and inclusive community or citizenship participation in urban planning	the main barriers of the research is than the issue of participation is an issue in construction, is transforming itself every day and it is difficult to define the end.		the methodology of the research is based in three main components: a review of the concept of participation in general, the development of the concept internationally and in Chile and the concept of local urban management. The second component is the description, characterization and selection of the cases studies from the 13 municipalities that integrated the Network for Participation., and the third one is the interview of different staff members of the municipalities.	We select 2 cases studies: the municipality of Santiago and Providencia FAU		Participatory Processes in the multi-scale: housing, neighbourhood and city. Subject for architectural students from 3 year, 1 semester Participatory Planning in the urban local management: subject for students from different faculties and careers, at university level, 1 semester		FAU

6 APPENDIX B: MATRIX 2: MAPPING RESEARCH THEMES TO OUTPUTS

OIKONET REVISED RESEARCH MATRIX				V2	SUBNETWORK WP2		30/06/2016
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activities that have informed OIKONET (research, pedagogy, participation) and have led to a particular academic publication.</p>							
Research concept	Description	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	OIKOPEDIA	Reader 1	Reader 2	Other publication
The research concepts that have emerged as critical and necessary to understand the global dimension of housing.	A brief description of the research concept or theme.	Pedagogic activities that have been informed by this concept.	Participation activities that have been informed by this concept.	OIKOPEDIA entries connected to this concept.	Sections in Reader 1 that have covered this concept.	Sections in Reader 2 that have covered this concept.	Other publications that related to this concept and its link to OIKONET activities.
Sustainability							
Sustainable or green building construction of housing	It endorses the principals of sustainable development in the siting, design, building, maintenance and occupation of buildings.			Urban greening Urban heat islands mitigation		Chapter 2	World Renewable Energy Congress WREC XIV paper
Energy efficiency in housing	Is concerned with energy performance and is one key aspect influenced by design and cuts across several facets of the society such as social, economic and environmental.			Passive Design (RTU)	Chapter 3	Chapter 5	
Sustainable housing design	Conserve energy, reduce the waste generation and be environmentally equitable.			Sustainable Design. Sustainable Design - learning by doing.	Chapter 1		
Socially sustainable transformation of communities and cities	Maintaining social cohesion and ensuring citizens participation during and after urban transformations.	Learning space "Urban Systems"		Sustainable Communities, Capacity-building, Interplace, Codesign	Chapter 2	Chapter 7, Chapter 3	
Economic sustainability	Creating affordable or social housing projects that are economically sustainable in the long term. This means the ability to support or continue indefinitely, without economic repercussions.			Sustainable Communities; Housing innovations; Public Rental Housing Programme as Innovation - Brief	Chapter 6	Chapter 6	
Participation							
Community, users or citizens' participation	Aims at taking into account inhabitants' requirements in housing design and planning.	Learning space "Civic Housing"	Participatory action "Civic Housing"	Participatory Planning (RTU), Capacity-building, Interplace, Codesign	Chapter 2	Chapter 7, Chapter 3, Chapter 6 (IHS, RTU)	
Citizens' empowerment	Inhabitants are key actors in governance processes aimed at developing the city.			Capacity-building, Interplace, Codesign	Chapter 2	Chapter 7	

OIKONET REVISED RESEARCH MATRIX				V2	SUBNETWORK WP2	30/06/2016	
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activities that have informed OIKONET (research, pedagogy, participation) and have led to a particular academic publication.</p>							
Research concept	Description	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	OIKOPEDIA	Reader 1	Reader 2	Other publication
The research concepts that have emerged as critical and necessary to understand the global dimension of housing.	A brief description of the research concept or theme.	Pedagogic activities that have been informed by this concept.	Participation activities that have been informed by this concept.	OIKOPEDIA entries connected to this concept.	Sections in Reader 1 that have covered this concept.	Sections in Reader 2 that have covered this concept.	Other publications that related to this concept and its link to OIKONET activities.
Codesign	Includes design involvement in aesthetics, place-making, and public space.		Participatory action "Civic Housing"	Capacity-building, Interplace, Codesign	Chapter 2	Chapter 7	"Co-operation in urban renewal projects: Students' participation in transformation process of large-scale housing areas". The first OIKONET conference, conference paper (RTU). "Case Study of CPTED Workshop in Riga: Creating links between learning practice and stakeholders in the process of urban refurbishment" (RTU). The second OIKONET conference on "Global Dwelling", conference poster.
Changing established power structures	Participation is being used as a mechanism to preserve existing political structures rather than to radically transform them		Participatory action in Rimini			Chapter 7	
Spacepower	Established groups take it for granted, other groups can claim or reclaim. And spacepower can emerge.			Interspace, codesign		Chapter 6,7 and 8	Ognen Marina and the Oikonetwork in Skopje lives the concept
Affordable housing							
Affordable mass social housing	Low-cost mass housing built during the second half of 20th century.			Social Housing in the (developing) World			
Overcrowding	A lack of affordable housing forcing many young adults to live with their parents and grandparents sometimes in substandard housing.			Housing Rights			
Integration and social cohesion	Access to decent affordable housing is a fundamental determinant of people's welfare.		Participatory activity in Rimini	Housing Rights	Chapter 1		
Social innovation programmes	They aim to facilitate access to housing to young households.		Participatory activity in Rimini	Housing innovations; Public Rental Housing Programme as Innovation - Brief	Chapter 6	Chapter 10	
Accessibility	Elderly inhabitants are living in apartments they cannot longer access (upper floor flats, maisonettes with staircases,...). Likewise they cannot access the public spaces because of the difficulty to leave the flat.				Chapter 1		

OIKONET REVISED RESEARCH MATRIX				V2	SUBNETWORK WP2		30/06/2016
<p>The purpose of this research matrix is to record research activities that have informed OIKONET (research, pedagogy, participation) and have led to a particular academic publication.</p>							
Research concept	Description	PEDAGOGY	PARTICIPATION	OIKOPEDIA	Reader 1	Reader 2	Other publication
<p>The research concepts that have emerged as critical and necessary to understand the global dimension of housing.</p>	<p>A brief description of the research concept or theme.</p>	<p>Pedagogic activities that have been informed by this concept.</p>	<p>Participation activities that have been informed by this concept.</p>	<p>OIKOPEDIA entries connected to this concept.</p>	<p>Sections in Reader 1 that have covered this concept.</p>	<p>Sections in Reader 2 that have covered this concept.</p>	<p>Other publications that related to this concept and its link to OIKONET activities.</p>
Informal housing	<p>For various reasons there may not be affordable housing available in communities. This can lead to people building informal housing (especially in urban areas)</p>	Lisbon Workshop		Resettlement, Housing Rights		Chapter 1	
<p>Housing regeneration</p>							
Urban regeneration	<p>Historically focussed on social and economic improvement, and nowadays with more emphasis on sustainable development.</p>	Belgrade workshop Renewable cities- Learning Space Housing Regeneration- Learning Space Urban Systems		Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) (RTU) Public Open Space in Housing Areas (RTU)		Chapter 1	Liverpool conference paper & Journal Publication.
Brownfield redevelopment	<p>It is a redevelopment option for housing development programmes using previously developed land.</p>			Brownfield regeneration.		Chapter 1	
Refurbishment/retrofitting	<p>Improvement of energy performance of old housing stock through façade thermal insulation, window replacement and thermal insulation of constructions for unheated basements and attics.</p>			Passive Design (RTU)	Chapter 3	Chapter 5	
Bringing together social and physical structures	<p>There is a split between both structures due to changes in family structures, aging population, impossibility to refurbish existing building stock...</p>	Learning Space "Urban Systems"					
Integration of domestic and public spaces	<p>Housing is an integral part of the city. The ties between domestic and public spaces are sometimes broken and need to be reinstaured</p>	Learning Space "Urban Systems"					

7 APPENDIX C: BIBLIOGRAPHY

7.1 Urban Regeneration

Svamala case, primary sources from the field, secondary sources: Journals
Capacity issues in local communities for integral urban regeneration , Arhitektura i Urbanizam, 2013, iss. 38, pp. 9-16, author: Tatjana Mrdjenovic,
Urban regeneration: Questioning the subject, Technics Technologies Education Management –TTEM (Thompson, Web of science, Web of knowledge, etc), Vol.8, No3., 8/9.2013., author: Tatjana Mrđenović,
Designing/Modeling the Space for Urban Regeneration: Pros and Cons, Technics Technologies Education Management –TTEM (Thompson, Web of science, Web of knowledge, etc), Vol.8, No4., 11/13.2013., authors: Tatjana Mrđenović, Miodrag Ralević, (paper accepted 10.04.2013)
Integrative urban design in regeneration – Principles for achieving sustainable places, Journal of Applied Engineerind Science, ISSN 1451-4117, УДК 33, број рада 9(2011)2,196,305-316, author: Tatjana Mrđenović, http://issuu.com/iipp/docs/2_2011_9
Books
Urban regeneration of protected ambients in the context of sustainable development – Bač Fortress Suburbium, author: Tatjana Mrđenović; group of authors: Jelica Jovanović, Mila Pucar, Ana Radivojević, Slavica Vujović, Dragana Petrović, Dragana Marjanović, publisher University of Belgrade – Faculty of Architecture, 2011, financed by Ministry of education and science, Republic of Serbia http://obavezni.digital.nb.rs/izdovac/af/publikacija/11
Books chapters
Urban regeneration and integrative urban design: Challenges for Serbian legislative framework/ Urbana regeneracija i integrativni urbani dizajn: Izazovi za srpski zakonodavni okvir, (2012) author: Tatjana Mrđenović In. Climate Change and the Built Environment: Policies and Practice in Scotland and Serbia / Klimatske promene i građena sredina: Politike i praksa u Škotskoj i Srbiji, ed. Mila Pucar, Branka Dimitrijević, Igor Marić
Urban regeneration and integrative urban design: Challenges for Serbian teaching practice / Urbana regeneracija i integrativni urbani dizajn: Izazovi za edukacione procese u Srbiji, (2012) author: Tatjana Mrđenović In. Climate Change and the Built Environment: Policies and Practice in Scotland and Serbia / Klimatske promene i građena sredina: Politike i praksa u Škotskoj i Srbiji, ed. Mila Pucar, Branka Dimitrijević, Igor Marić ,

7.2 Energy

Adetunji, I., Price, A., Fleming, P., and Kemp, P., 2003. Sustainability and the UK construction industry - a review. <i>Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers, Engineering Sustainability</i> , 156 (4), 185-199.
Akimoto et al. (2010a). Thermal comfort and productivity - Evaluation of workplace environment in a task conditioned office, <i>International Symposium on the Interaction between Human and Building Environment Special Issue Section, Building and Environment</i> , 45 (1), 45- 50.
Anink, D., Boonstra, C., and Mak, J., 1996. <i>Handbook of sustainable building: an environmental preference method for selection of materials for use in construction and refurbishment</i> . Earthscan Publications.
Building Research Establishment - BRE, 2002. <i>MaSC guide: profiting from sustainability</i> . London: BRE.
BS EN 15251 (2007) <i>Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics</i> . London; British Standards Institute.
Cena, K. and de Dear, R. (2001). Thermal comfort and behavioural strategies in office buildings located in a hot-arid climate, <i>Journal of Thermal Biology</i> , 26 (4-5), 409 – 414.
CIBSE Guide A: (2006). <i>Guide A: Environmental design</i> . London: Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers (CIBSE).
CIBSE Guide F: (2012). <i>Guide F: Energy Efficiency in Buildings</i> . London: Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers (CIBSE).
Dair, C. M. and Williams, K., 2006. Sustainable land reuse: the influence of different stakeholders in achieving sustainable brownfield developments in England. <i>Environment and Planning A</i> , 38 , 1345-1366.
de Dear, R., Barger, R.J., 1998. Developing and adaptive model of thermal comfort and preference. <i>ASHRAE Transactions</i> , 104(1), 145-167
de Dear, R. 2009. The theory of thermal comfort in naturally ventilated indoor environments-“the pleasure principle”. <i>International Journal of ventilation</i> , 8(3), 243-250.
Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions - DETR, 2000. <i>Building a better quality of life: A strategy for more sustainable construction</i> . London.
Eurofound, (2011), Accessed on 21/09/2013, http://www.eurofound.europa.eu/areas/industrialrelations/dictionary/definitions/workingconditions.htm
Freeman, R. (2008). <i>Labour productivity indicators</i> . OECD.
Gun, R. T. and Budd, G. M. (1995), Effects of thermal, personal and behavioural factors on the physiological strain, thermal comfort and productivity of Australian shearers in hot weather, <i>Ergonomics</i> , 38 (7), 1368-1384.
Hill, R. C. and Bowen, P. A., 1997. Sustainable construction: principles and a framework for attainment. <i>Construction Management and Economics</i> , 15 (3), 223-239.
Huizenga, C. et al. (2006). <i>Air quality and thermal comfort in office buildings: Results of a large indoor environmental quality survey</i> , <i>Indoor Environmental Quality</i> . Centre for the Built Environment, UC Berkeley.
Huizenga, C., Laeser, K and Arens, E. (2002). <i>A Web-Based Occupant Satisfaction Survey for Benchmarking Building Quality</i> . <i>Indoor Air 2002</i> . Monterey, CA.
Hummelgaard, J., Juhl, P., Sæbjørnsson, K.O., Clausen, G., Toftum, J., Langkilde, G., 2007. Indoor air quality and occupant satisfaction in five mechanically and four naturally ventilated open-plan office buildings. <i>Building and Environment</i> , 42 (12), 4051-4058
Liddament, M.W., 1996. <i>A guide to energy efficient ventilation</i> , Warwick: Air Infiltration and Ventilation Centre (AIVC)
Lowe, G. S. (2003). Healthy Workplaces and Productivity: A Discussion Paper, Economic Analysis and Evaluation Division, Health Canada, Accessed on the 11th of Sept 2013, http://www.nqi.ca/assets/files/products/healthy_20workplaces_productivity-english_20report.pdf
Moujalled, B. Cantin, R. Guarracino, G. 2008. Comparison of thermal comfort algorithms in naturally ventilated office buildings. <i>Energy and Buildings</i> , 40(12), 2215-2223
Nicol, F. and Roaf, S. (2005). Post-occupancy evaluation and field studies of thermal comfort, <i>Building Research and Information</i> , Special Issue: Building Performance Evaluation, 33 (4), 338-346.
Nicol, JF and Humphreys M (2002) Adaptive thermal comfort and sustainable thermal standards for buildings. <i>Energy and Buildings</i> 34, 563-572
Singh, M.K. Mahapatra, S. Aterya, S.K. 2011. Adaptive thermal comfort for different climatic zones of north east India. <i>Applied energy</i> , 88(7), 2420-2428.
Venters, W., Cornford, T., and Cushman, M., 2005. Knowledge about sustainability: SSM as a method for conceptualising the UK construction industry's knowledge environment. <i>CIT Journal of Computing and Information Technology</i> , 13 (2), 137-148.

7.3 Indoor air quality

Appleton, N. (1993) "Sheltered accommodation for elderly people in Great Britain". In G. Dooghe, & L. Vanden Boer (eds), "Sheltered accommodation for elderly people in an international perspective", (pp. 7-36). Amsterdam: Swets & Zeitlinger.

Arksey, H., O' Malley, L., (2005), 'Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework', International Journal Social Research Methodology, Vol. 8, Issue 1, pp. 19-32.

Bonnefoy, X. (2007), 'Inadequate housing and health: an overview', International Journal of Environment and Pollution, 419-429.

Brawley, E.C. (2006), 'Design innovations for aging and Alzheimer's creating caring environments'. John Wiley.

BSI. (2002) "BS 5250:2002. Code of practice for control of condensation in buildings". London: British Standard Institute.

Carp, F.M. (1967) "The impact of environment on old people". The Gerontologist, 7, 106-8.

Coelho, C., Steers, M., Lutzler, P., Schriver-Mazzuoli, L., (2005) "Indoor air pollution in old people's homes related to some health problems: a survey study", Indoor Air, Blackwell Publishing, 15: 267-274.

Croucher, K. (2008), 'Housing choices and aspirations of older people'. Centre for Housing Policy, University of York, Communities and Local Government publications.

Crump, D., Dengel, A., Swainson, M. (2009) "Indoor Air Quality in Highly Energy Efficient Homes - A Review", NHBC Foundation Report NF19, HIS BRE Press, Watford, UK.

EEA (2011) "Air quality in Europe - 2011 report". EEA Technical report No 12/2011, Copenhagen: European Environment Agency.

EFA. Report of the event "Indoor Air Quality and its Effects on Health: a Presentation of the Guidelines for Health-Based Ventilation in Europe", European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations. Available from: <http://www.efanet.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/03/HealthVent-event-Report-FINAL.pdf>

Energy Saving Trust. (2006) "Energy efficient ventilation in dwellings - a guide for specifiers: GPG268". Energy Saving Trust.

Evans, G.W. (2003), 'The built environment and mental health'. Journal of Urban Health, 80(4), 536-555.

Fleming R., Crookes, P., and Sum, S. (2009), 'A review of the empirical literature on the design of physical environments for people with dementia'. Australia: The University of New South Wales.

Freidl, W., Imler, A., Koch, M., Schmidt, R., Stronegger, W.J., (1996), 'Mini mental state examination: influence of socio-demographic, environmental and behavioural factors, and vascular risk factors'. Journal of Clinical Epidemiology, Elsevier Science Incorporation, 49(1), 73-78.

Gilleard, C., Hyde, M. & Higgs, P. (2007) "The impact of age, place, aging in place, and attachment to place on the well-being of the over 50s in England". Research on Aging, 29 (6), 590-605.

Hadjri, K. & Crozier, C. (2009), 'Post-Occupancy Evaluation: Purpose, Benefits and Barriers'. Facilities, 27(1/2), pp. 21-33.

Hadjri, K. (2010), 'An assessment of sheltered housing design in Belfast, Northern Ireland'. Journal of Housing for the Elderly, 24(2), 171-192.

Hills, J. (2007) "Ends and means: the future roles of social housing in England". CASE report 34. February. ESRC Research Centre for Analysis of Social Exclusion.

Hunt, A. (1978) "The elderly at home". A survey carried out on behalf of the Department of Health and Social Security by the Office of Population Censuses and Surveys. London: Her Majesty's Stationery Office HMSO.

Hwang, R.L., Chen, C.P. (2010) "Field Study on behaviours and adaption of elderly people and their thermal comfort requirements in residential environments", Indoor Air, John Wiley and Sons, 20: 235-245.

Jantunen, M., et al. (2011) "Promoting actions for healthy indoor air (IAIAQ)". Luxembourg: European Commission Directorate General for Health and Consumers.

Jones, G., and Van der Eerden, W. J. (2008), 'Designing care environments for people with Alzheimer's Disease: Visuoperceptual considerations'. Cambridge University Press.

Joseph, A. (2006), 'Health promotion by design in long term care settings'. The centre for Health Design.

ONS (2010) "Ageing across the UK. Office for National Statistics". By James Bayliss and Frances Sly. Regional Trends 42: 2010 edition.

Parker, C., Barnes, S., Mckee, K., Morgan, K., Torrington, J. (2004), 'Quality of life and building design in residential and nursing homes for older people'. Ageing & Society, 24, 941-962.

Passini R., Rainville C., Marchand N., Joannette Y. (1998) Wayfinding and dementia: some research findings and a new look at design. Journal of Architectural and Planning Research, 15(2), 133-151.

Passini, R., Pigot, H., Rainville, C., Tétreault, M-H. (2000), 'Wayfinding in a nursing home for advanced dementia of the Alzheimer's type'. Environment and Behaviour, 32, pp. 684-710.

Pawson, H., & Wilcox S. (2013) "UK Housing Review". The Chartered Institute of Housing.

Reidlich, C. A., Sparer, J., Cullen, M. J. (1997) "Sick-Building Syndrome". The Lancet, 349, pp. 1013-1016

Slezakova, K., Morais, S., do Carmo Pereira, M. (2012) "Indoor Air Pollutants: Relevant Aspects and Health Impacts, Environmental Health - Emerging Issues and Practice". In Tech.

Smith, J., Dellinger, B., Guenther, R., Simeonova, M., Perlman, J., Knoop, S.L., Huelat, B. (2004), 'The elements of a caring environment'. Healthcare Design, Sept.

Smith, L. & Swan, W. (2012) "Delivery of Retrofit at Scale: Developing a viable delivery model in social housing", in: 'Retrofit 2012', University of Salford, Salford, UK, 24th - 26th January 2012.

Torrington, J., (2007), 'Evaluating quality of life in residential care buildings'. Building research and information, 35(5), 514-528.

van Hoof, J., & Kort, H.S.M. (2008), 'Designing a supportive living environment for older people with dementia', IFA's Global Conference on Ageing, Montreal, Canada.

WHO (2006) "Air Quality Guidelines - global Update 20052. Copenhagen: World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe.

WHO (2009) "WHO guidelines for indoor air quality: dampness and mould". Copenhagen: World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe.

Ahmed K.S. 1994. A comparative analysis of the outdoor thermal environment of the urban vernacular and the contemporary development: case studies in Dhaka. V: Etzion Y in sod. (ur). Architecture of the extremes. Ben-Gurion. University of the Negev 341-348.

Alli-Toudert F., Mayer H. 2007. Effects of asymmetry, galleries, overhanging facades and vegetation on thermal comfort in urban street canyons. *Solar energy* 81:742-754.

Apte, M.G., Fisk, W.J. and Daisey, J.M. 2000. Associations between indoor CO2 concentrations and sick building syndrome symptoms in US office buildings: an analysis of the 1994-1996 BASE study data, *Indoor Air*, 10: 246–257.

Asaeda T., Ca V.T. 1993. The subsurface transport of heat and moisture and its effect on the environment: a numerical model. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology* 65:159-179.

Ballester F., Corella D., Perez-Hoyos S., Saez M., Hervás A. 1997. Mortality as a function of temperature. A study in Valencia, Spain, 1991-1993. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 26:551-561.

Basu R., Samet J.M. 2002. Relation between elevated ambient temperature and mortality: a review of the epidemiologic evidence. *Epidemiological Review*, 24 (2): 1219-1224.

Beckett P.K., Freer-Smith P., Taylor G. 2000. The capture of particulate pollution by trees at five contrasting urban sites. *Arboricultural Journal*, 24: 209-230.

Beddhu S., Nigwekar S.U., Ma X., Greene T. 2009. Associations of resting heart rate with insulin resistance, cardiovascular events and mortality in chronic kidney disease. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*, 24: 2482-2488.

Beere P.A., Glagov S., Zarins C.K. 1984. Retarding effect of lowered heart rate on coronary atherosclerosis. *Science*, 226:180-182.

Boersma E., Pieper K.S., Steyerberg E.W., Wilcox R.G., Chang W.C., Lee K.L., Akkerhuis K.M., Harrington R.A., Deckers J.W., Armstrong P.W., Lincoff A.M., Califf R.M., Topol E.J., Simoons M.L. 2000. Predictors of outcome in patients with acute coronary syndromes without persistent ST-segment elevation. Results from an international trial of 9461 patients. The PURSUIT Investigators. *Circulation*, 101:2567–2567.

Böhm M., Swedberg K., Komajda M., Borer JS., Ford I., Dubost-Brama A., Lerebours G., Tavazzi L. 2010. Heart rate as risk factor in chronic heart failure (SHIFT): the association between heart rate and outcomes in a randomized placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*, 376:886-894.

Bonan G.B. 2000. The microclimates of suburban Colorado (USA) landscape and implications for planning and design. *Landscape and Urban Planning* 49: 97-114.

Bourbia F., Awbi H.B. 2004. Building cluster and shading in urban canyon for hot dry climate. Part 1: Air and surface temperature measurements. *Renewable Energy* 29:249-262.

Braga A.L., Zanobetti A., Schwartz J. 2002. The effect of weather on respiratory and cardiovascular deaths in 12 US cities. *Environmental Health Prospects*, 110:859– 63.

Bruse M. 2012. ENVI-met 3.1 BETA 5. A Micro scale Urban Climate Model. <http://www.envi-met.com/> [11.10.2012]

Bueno-Bartholomei C.L., Labaki L.C. 2003. How much does the change of species of trees affect their solar radiation attenuation? V: Fifth International Conference on Urban Climate, Lodz, Poljska.

Ca V.T., Asaeda T., Abu E.M. 1998. Reductions in air conditioning energy caused by nearby park. *Energy and Buildings* 29:83-92.

Cakmak S., Dales R.E., Rubio M.A., Vidal C.B. 2011. The risk of dying on days of higher air pollution among socially disadvantaged elderly. *Environmental research*, 111:388-393.

Cavanagh J.E., Zavar-Rezab P., Wilson J.G. 2009. Spatial attenuation of ambient particulate matter air pollution within an urbanised native forest patch. *Urban Forest Urban Green*, 8:21-30.

Chan A.T., So E.S.P., Samad A.C. 2001. Strategic guidelines for street canyon geometry to achieve sustainable street air quality. *Atmospheric Environment* 35:5681-5691.

Chen C.P., Hwang R.L., Chang S.Y., Lu Y.T. 2011. Effects of temperatures on human skin physiology and thermal sensation response. *Building Environment*, 46(11): 2387-2397.

Chen Y., Wong N.H. 2006. Thermal benefits of city parks. *Energy and Buildings* 38:105-120.

Cohen P., Potchter O., Matzarakis A. 2012. Daily and seasonal climatic conditions of green urban open spaces in the Mediterranean climate and their impact on human comfort. *Building and Environment* 51: 285-295.

Correa E. Ruiz M.A., Canton A., Lesino G. 2012. Thermal comfort in forested urban canyons of low building density. An assessment for the city of Mendoza, Argentina. *Building and Environment* 58:219-230.

Dhainaut J.F., Claessens Y.E., Ginsburg C., Riou B. 2004. Unprecedented heat-related deaths during the 2003 heat wave in Paris: consequences on emergency departments. *Critical Care*, 8:1-2.

Dolinar M., Vidrih B., Kajfež-Bogataj L., Medved S. 2010. Predicted changes in energy demand for heating and cooling due to climate change. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth*, 35:100-106.

Escobedo F.J., Nowak D.J. 2009. Spatial heterogeneity and air pollution removal by an urban forest. *Landscape Urban Planning*, 90:102:110.

Fink R., Eržen I., Medved S. 2012. Environmentally induced health impacts among elderly with cardio-vascular disease. *HealthMed* 6 (11):3841-3849.

Fujii S., Cha H., Kagi N., Miyamura H., Kim Y.S. 2005. Effects on air pollutant removal by plant absorption and adsorption. *Building and Environment*, 40: 105-112.

Gaffin S.L., Hubbard R.W. 2001. Pathophysiology of heatstroke. V: Pandolf K.B., Burr R.E. (ur). Medical aspects of harsh environments. Vol.1. USA, Government Printing Office. 161-208.

Georgi N.J. Zafriadis K. 2006. The impact of park trees on microclimate in urban areas. *Urban Ecosystems* 9:195-209.

Ghenu A., Rosant J.M., Sini J.F. 2008. Dispersion of pollutants and estimation of emissions in a street canyon in Rouen, France. *Environmental modelling & Software* 23: 314-321.

Goodman P.G., Dockery D.W., Clancy L. 2004. Cause-specific mortality and the extended effects of particulate pollution and temperature exposure. *Environmental Health Prospects*, 112:179 185.

Gosling S., Lowe J., McGregor G., Pelling M., Malamud B. 2009. Associations between elevated atmospheric temperature and human mortality: a critical review of the literature. *Climate Change*, 92(3):299–341.

Haines A., Kovats R.S., Campbell-Lendrum D., Corvalan C. 2006. Climate change and human health: impacts, vulnerability, and mitigation. *Lancet*, 367: 2101-2109.

Hamada S., Ohta T. 2010. Seasonal variations in the cooling effect of green areas on surrounding urban areas. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 9: 15-24.

Harrabi I., Rondeau V., Dartigues J.F., Tessier J.F., Filleul L. 2006. Effects of particulate air pollution on systolic blood pressure: a population based approach. *Environmental Research*, 101: 89-93.

Havenith G. 2005. Temperature Regulation, Heat Balance and Climatic Stress. V: Kirch W., Monne B., Bertolini R(ur). Extreme Weather Events and Public Health Responses. Springer. Berlin Heidelberg New York. 69-80.

Hoffmann B., Hertel S., Boes T., Weiland D, Jöckel K.H 2008. Increased cause-specific mortality associated with 2003 heat wave in Essen, Germany. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part A*, 71:759-765.

Hunter, L.J., Johnson, G.T., Watson I.D. 1992. An investigation of three-dimensional characteristics of flow regimes within the urban canyon. *Atmospheric Environment*, 26B (4): 425-432.

Ibald-Mulli A., Timonen K.L., Peters A., Heinrich J., Wölke G., Lanke T., Buzorius G., Kreyling W.G., de Hartog J., Hoek G., ten Brink H.M., Pekkanen J. 2004. Effects of particulate air pollution on blood pressure and heart rate in subjects with cardiovascular disease: A multicenter approach. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 112(3): 259-377.

Inaba R., Mirbod S.R. 2007. Comparison of subjective symptoms and hot prevention measures in summer between traffic control workers and construction workers in Japan. *Industrial Health Journal*, 45: 91-999.

Inoue Y., Nakao M., Okudaira S., Ueda H., Araki T. 1995. Seasonal variation in sweating responses of older and younger men. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 70: 6-12.

Johansson E. 2006. Influence of urban geometry on outdoor thermal comfort in a hot dry climate: A study in Fez, Morocco. *Building and Environment*, 40 (10): 1326-1338.

Johnson W.B., Ludwig F.L., Dabberdt W.F., Allen R.J. 1973. An Urban Diffusion Simulation Model for Carbon Monoxide. *Journal of the Air Pollution Control Association*, 23(6): 490-498.

Karatasou S., Santamoris M., Geros V. 2006. Urban Building Climatology. V: Santamouris M. (ur). Environmental Design of Urban Buildings. An Integrated Approach. Earthscan. London. 95-119.

SIST EN ISO 9886: 2004 Vrednotenje toplotnih obremenitev s pomočjo fizioloških meritev. Mednarodna organizacija za standardizacijo. 21 str.

SIST EN ISO 13779: 2005. Prezračevanje nestanovanjskih stavb-Zahtevane lastnosti za prezračevalne naprave in klimatizirane sisteme. 52 str.

SIST EN ISO 7730:2006. Ergonomija toplotnega okolja - Analitično ugotavljanje in interpretacija toplotnega ugodja z izračunom PMV in PPD vrednosti ter merili za lokalno toplotno ugodje. 52 str.

Stewart H., Owen S., Donovan R., MacKenzie R., Hewitt N. 2002. Trees and sustainable urban air quality. Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, Lancaster University. Dostopno na [<http://www.es.lancs.ac.uk/people/cnh/docs/UrbanTrees.htm>.] [Citirano 2012 Dec].

Taha H. 2008. Meso-urban meteorological and photochemical modelling of heat island mitigation. *Atmospheric Environment*, 42(38):8795–809.

Taha H.G. 1978. An urban Micro-Climate Model for site specific building energy simulation: boundary layers, Urban Canyon and building conditions. Department of Architecture, University of California: Berkeley, CA 135.

TenWolde A., Pilon C.L. 2007. The Effect of Indoor Humidity on Water Vapour Release in Homes. *ASHRAE Buildings X*, 1-9.

Terjung W.H., Louie S.S.F. 1974. A climatic model of urban energy budgets. *Geographical Analysis* 6: 341-367.

Terjung W.H., O'Rourke P.A. 1981. Energy input and resultant surface temperatures for individual urban interfaces, selected latitudes and seasons. *Archives for Meteorology, Geophysics, and Bioclimatology B* 29:1-22.

Theoharatos G., Pantavou K., Mavrakis A., Spanou A., Katavoutas G., Efstathiou P., Mpekas P., Asimakopoulos D. 2010. Heat waves observed in 2007 in Athens, Greece: Synoptic conditions, bio-climatological assessment, air quality levels and health effects. *Environmental Research*, 110: 152-161.

Tian Z., Zhu N., Zheng G., Wei H. 2011. Experimental study on physiological effects of heat acclimatization in extreme hot environments. *Building and environment*, 46: 2033-2041.

Tomalak M., Rossi E., Ferrini F., Moro P.A. 2011. Native aspects and hazardous effects of forest environment on human health. V: Nilsson K., Sangster M., Gallis C., Harting T., de Vries S., Seeland K., Schipperijn J. (ur). *Forest, trees and human health*. Springer Science+Business Media 77-126.

TRNSYS. 2000. A Transient Simulation Program, Version 15. Solar Energy Laboratory. University of Wisconsin.

Urch B., Silverman F., Corey P., Brook J.R., Lukic K.Z., Rajagopalan S., Brook R.D. 2005. Acute blood pressure responses in healthy adults during controlled air pollution. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 113(8): 1052-1055.

Vardoulakis S., Fisher B.E.A., Pericleous K., Gonzalez-Flesca N. 2003. Modelling air quality in street canyons: a review. *Atmospheric Environment*, 37: 155-182.

Vidrih B. 2011. Vpliv globalnih podnebni sprememb in urbanizacije na lokalne razmere v mestnem okolju. Doktorsko delo. Mentor: prof.dr. Sašo Medved. Univerza v Ljubljani, Fakulteta za strojništvo. 134 str.

Vidrih B., Medved S. 2013. Multiparametric model of urban park cooling island. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* (v tisku).

Vlahov D., Boufford J.Y., Pearson C., Norris L. 2010. *Urban Health. Global Perspectives*. Jossey-bass A Wiley Imprint, USA. 500 str.

Xiaomin X., Zhen H., Jiasong W. 2006. The impact of urban street layout on local atmospheric environment. *Building and Environment* 41 (10): 1352-1363.

Yang J., McBride J., Zhou J.X., Sun Z.Y. 2005. The urban forest in Beijing and its role in air pollution reduction. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 3:65-78.

Yassin M.F. 2011. Impact of high and shape of building roof on air quality in urban street canyons. *Atmospheric Environment* 45:5220-5229.

Yin S, Cai J.P., Chen L.P., Shen Z.M., Zou X.D., Dan W., Wenhua W. 2007. Effects of vegetation status in urban green spaces on particle removal in a street canyon atmosphere. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 27(11):4590-4595.

Yohe G., Elbi K.L. 2005. Approaching adaptation: parallels and contrasts between the climate and health communities. V: Ebi L., Smith J., Burton I. (ur). *Integration of public health with adaptation to climate change. Lessons learned and new directions*. Taylor & Francis, Lieden, The Netherlands 18-43.

Younger M., Morrow-Ameida H.R., Vindigni S.M., Dannenberg A.L. 2008. The built environment, climate change, and health. Opportunities for Co-Benefits. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 35(5): 517-526.

7.4 Mobility

- Afacan, Y. (2008). Computer assisted universal design (caud) plug-in tool for architectural design process. Dissertation, Bilkent University: Turkey.
- Andrews, B. (2008). 'Lifetime homes, lifetime neighbourhoods- developing a housing strategy for our ageing population'. *Policy and Politics*, 36 (4), pp. 605-610.
- Arksey, H. & O'Malley, L. (2005). 'Scoping Studies: Towards a Methodological Framework'. *Int. J.Social Research Methodology*, 8 (1), pp. 19-32.
- Barker, P. Barrick, J. & Wilson, R. (1995). *Building Sight A handbook of building and interior design solutions to include the needs of visually impaired people*. London: HMSO.
- Barlow, J. & Venables, T. (2004). 'Will Technological Innovation Create the True Lifetime Home?' *Housing Studies*, 19 (5), 795-810.
- Brewerton, J. & Darton, D. (1997). *Designing Lifetime Homes*. York: Joseph Rowntree Foundation.
- Bury, R. (2010, Nov). Building drive will cut social housing. Homepage of Inside Housing. Retrieved January 26, 2006 from <http://www.insidehousing.co.uk/news/development/building-drive-will-cut-social-housing/6512412.article>
- Carrol, C. Cowans, J. & Darton, D. (1999). *Meeting Part M and designing Lifetime Homes*. York: Joseph Rowntree Foundation.
- CRD. (2001). *Undertaking Systematic Reviews of Research on Effectiveness: CRD's Guidance for those Carrying Out or Commissioning Reviews*. CRD Report 4, 2nd edn. York: University of York, NHS Centre for Reviews and Dissemination.
- Davis, K. Drey, N. & Gould, D. (2009). 'What are scoping studies? A review of the nursing literature'. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 46, pp. 1386-1400.
- Department for Communities and Local Government, Department of Health and Department for Work and Pensions. (2008). *Lifetime Homes, Lifetime Neighbourhoods A National Strategy for Housing in an Ageing Society*. Yorkshire: Communities and Local Government Publications.
- Dewsbury, G.A. & Edge, H.M. (2000, June). Designing the Home to Meet the Needs of Tomorrow... Today: Deconstructing and rebuilding the home for life. In: ENHR conference. 26-30 June, ENHR: Gavle Sweden.
- Donnelly, M. (2009, July). *Lifetime Adaptable Homes Seminar. (Paper Presented at the Centre for Excellence in Universal Design, Seminar: Lifetime Homes in Policy and Practice, Dublin)*. Retrieved July 26, 2006, from <http://accessit.nda.ie/newsandevents/eventsarchive/seminarquotlifetimhomesinpolicyampractiquequot>
- Donald, I.P. (2009). 'Housing and health care for older people'. *Age and Ageing*, 38 (4), pp. 364-367.
- Evans, S. (2009). 'A response to Baroness Andrews, 'Lifetime homes, lifetimes neighbourhoods – developing a housing strategy for our ageing population'. *Policy and Politics*, 36, pp. 151-154.
- Frattari, A. Dalpra.M. & Chiogna, M. (2007). 'Smart home and architecture: The case study of dwellings for people with cognitive disabilities'. *Journal for Housing Science*, 31(2), 89-98.
- Goodridge, C. (2006). *Accessible London: achieving an inclusive environment Lifetime Homes (PDF)*, London: Greater London Authority. Retrived October 19, 2010, from <http://legacy.london.gov.uk/mayor/strategies/sds/docs/lifetime-homes.pdf>.
- Hanson, J. (2001). From Sheltered Housing to Lifetime Homes: an inclusive approach to housing. In: Winters, S, ed.2001. *Lifetime Housing in Europe*. Leuven: Katholieke Unversiteit Leuven. pp. 35-57.
- Hanson, J. & Percival, J. (2005). 'The housing and support needs of visually impaired adults living in England today'. *British Journal of Visual Impairment*, 23 (3), pp. 102- 107.
- Harding, E. (2007). *Towards Lifetime Neighbourhoods: Designing sustainable communities for all a discussion paper*. Yorkshire: Community and local Government Publications.
- Holland, C. & Peace, S. (2001). Inclusive housing. In S.Peace, & C. Holland eds.2001. *Inclusive Housing in an ageing society, Innovative approaches*. Bristol: The Policy Press. pp.235-261.
- Imrie, R. (2007). 'The interrelationship between building regulations and architects' practices'. *Environment and planning B: Planning Design*, 34(5), pp. 925-943.
- Imrie, R. (2006). 'Independent lives and the relevance of Lifetime homes'. *Disability & Society*, 4, pp.359-374.
- Imrie, R. (2004). 'The role of the building regulations in achieving housing quality'. *Environment and Planning and Design*, 31, pp. 419-437.
- Imrie, R. (2003). 'The impact of Part M on the design of new housing'. *Access by Design*, 96, pp. 6-8.
- Imrie, R. & Hall, P. (2001). *Inclusive Design Designing and Developing Accessible Environments*. New York: Spon Press.
- Imrie, R. (2000). 'Responding to the Design Needs of Disabled People'. *Journal of Urban Design*, 5(2), pp. 199-219.
- Joseph Rowntree foundation and Chartered Institute of Housing in Northern Ireland. (2002). *Lifetime Homes in Northern Ireland Evolution or Revolution?* Belfast: Chartered Institute of Housing in Northern Ireland.
- Kelly, M. (2001). *Lifetime Homes*. In: Peace, M.S. & Holland, C. eds, 2001. *Inclusive Housing in an ageing society, Innovative approaches*. Bristol: The Policy Press. p.p.55-77.
- Lansley, P. Flanagan, S. Goodacre, K. Turner-Smith, A. & Cowan, D. (2005). 'Assessing the adaptability of the existing homes of older people'. *Building and Environment*, 40 (7),pp. 949-963.
- Levac, D. Colquhoun, H. & O'Brien, K. (2010). Scoping Studies: advancing the methodology. [Electronic version]. *Implementation science*,5. Retrieved March 16, 2011, from <http://www.implementation-science.com/content/>
- Madigan, R. & Milner, J. (1999). 'Access for all: housing design and the Disability Discrimination Act 1995'. *Critical Social Policy*, 19 (3), pp. 396- 409.
- Milner, J. & Madigan, R. (2001). The politics of accessible housing in the UK. In Peace, S, & Holland, C. Eds. *Inclusive housing in an ageing society: innovative approaches*. Bristol: The Policy Press. pp. 77-101.
- Milner, J. & Madigan, R. (2004). 'Regulation and Innovation: Rethinking 'Inclusive' Housing Design'. *Housing Studies*, 19 (5), pp. 727-744.
- Monk, P. (2009). 'Homes for our lifetime needs'. *Access by design: the journal of the centre for accessible environments*, 118, pp. 22-30.
- NBS. (2010). *The construction information service briefing: UK November 2010*. Newcastle Upon Tyne: NBS.
- O'Malley, L. & Croucher, K. (2005). 'Supported Housing Services for People with Mental Health Problems: A Scoping Study'. *Housing Studies*, 20 (5), pp. 831-845.
- Ormerod, M. G. & Newton, R. (2005). 'Briefing for accessibility in design'. *Facilities*, 23 (7/8), pp. 285-294.
- Percival, J. (2002). 'Domestic spaces: uses and meanings in the daily lives of older people'. *Ageing and society*, 22, pp. 729-749.
- Preiser, WFE. & Ostroff, E. eds. (2001). *Universal Design Handbook*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Rooney, C., Faith, V., Hadjri, K. & Craig, C. (2011, April). *Cognitive disabilities: why the physical environment is important*. In: Include conference, 18-20 April, 2011. Helen Hamlyn Centre. London: Royal College of Art.
- Sopp, L. & Wood, L. (2001a). *Consumer and Industry views of Lifetime homes*. York: Joseph Rowntree foundation.
- Sopp, L. & Wood, L. (2001b). *Living in a Lifetime Home a Survey of residents' and developers' views*. York: York publishing Services Ltd.

7.5 Wayfinding

Akin, O., *Psychology of Architectural Design*, London: Pion Limited, 1986

Alzheimer's Society, 2011. *The £20 Billion Question: An Inquiry into Improving Lives Through Cost Effective Dementia Services*, Alzheimer's Society, London.

Américo, M. "Satisfacción residencial: Un análisis psicológico de la vivienda y su entorno". Madrid: Alianza, 1995.

Andrews, R., R. Cowell, J. Downe & S. Martin (2006). *Promoting Effective Citizenship and Community Empowerment: A Guide for Local Authorities on Enhancing Capacity for Public Participation*. Office of the Deputy Prime Minister.

Arnstein, Sherry (1969). 'A Ladder of Citizen Participation.' *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*(8): 216-224.

Banerjee, S., Smith, S. C., Lamping, D. L., Harwood, R. H., Foley, B., Smith, P., Murray, J., Prince, M., Levin, E., Mann, A. & Knapp, M., 2007. "Development of a new measure of health-related quality of life for people with dementia: DEMQOL". *Psychological Medicine*, 37, 737-746.

Beebejaun, Y. (2006) *The Participation Trap: The Limitations of Participation for Ethnic and Racial Groups*. *International Planning Studies* 11(1): 3-18.

Bonnefoy, X., 2007. "Inadequate housing and health: an overview". *International Journal of Environment and Pollution*, 30(3/4), 419-29.

Buchner, D.M.; Beresford, S.A.; Larson, E.B.; LaCroix, A.Z.; Wagner, E.H., 1992. "Effects of exercise on functional status in older adults: interventional studies". *Ann Rev Public Health*, 13, 469-488.

Burton, E; Mitchell, L. & Stride, C.B., 2011. "Good places for ageing in place: development of objective built environment measures for investigating links with older people's wellbeing". *BMC Public Health*, 11(839), 1-13.

Canter, D. *Interacción ambiental : aproximaciones psicológicas a nuestros entornos físicos*, London: The architectural press, 1977

Crampton, J; Dean, J. & Eley, R., 2012. *Creating a dementia-friendly York*. Joseph Rowntree Foundation, York. http://www.pdfdownload.org/pdf2html/view_online.php?url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.jrf.org.uk%2Fsites%2Ffiles%2Fjrf%2Fdementia-communities-york-full.pdf

Department of Health (DH), 2009. *Living Well with Dementia: A National Dementia Strategy*, COI and the Department of Health, London.

Department of Health, 2012. *Prime Minister's Challenge on Dementia: Delivering Major Improvements in Dementia Care and Research by 2015*, Department of Health, London, (produced by Williams Lea for the Department of Health), p. 3.

Department of Health, 2012. *The Prime Minister's Challenge on Dementia: Delivering major improvements in dementia care and research by 2015: A report on progress*. Department of Health, London, p.18. Available at www.dementiachallenge.dh.gov.uk

Dilani, A., 2001. "Psychosocially Supportive Design - as a Theory and Model to Promote Health". *Design and Health*. International Academy for Design and Health.

Hadžri, K.; Faith, V. & McManus, M., 2012. "Designing dementia nursing and residential care homes". *Journal of Integrated Care*. 20(5), 322-341, p.325.

Hamdi, N. (2004) *Small Change: About the Art of Practice and the Limits of Planning in Cities*. Eartscan.

Hendrie, H.C.; Albert, M.S.; Butters, M.A.; Gao, S.; Knopman, D.S.; Launer, L.J.; Yaffe, K.; Cuthbert, B.N.; Edwards, E. and Wagster, M.C., 2006. "The NIH Cognitive and Emotional Health Project: Report of the Critical Evaluation Study Committee". *Alzheimer's and Dementia*, 3, 12-32.

Hittner, J.B., 2007. "Factorial invariance of the 13-item Sense of Coherence scale across gender". *J Health Psychol*. 12, 273-80.

Jackson, R. J. & Kochitzky, C., 2001. "Creating A Healthy Environment: The Impact of the Built Environment on Public Health". Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, GA. *Sprawl Watch Clearinghouse Monograph Series*. Available at <http://www.sprawlwatch.org/health.pdf>

Kasser, V. G. & Ryan, R. M., 1999. "The relation of psychological needs for autonomy and relatedness to vitality, well-being, and mortality in a nursing home". *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 29(8), 935-54.

Kerse, N.; Hayman, K.J.; Moyes, S.A. et al., 2010. "Home-based activity program for older people with depressive symptoms: DeLLITE—a randomized controlled trial". *Ann Fam Med*, 8(3), 214-223.

Koltn, K.F., 2001. "The association between physical activity and quality of life in older women". *Women's Health Issues*, 11(6), 471-480.

Lane, M.B. (2003) *Participation, Decentralization, and Civil Society: Indigenous Rights and Democracy in Environmental Planning*. *Journal of Planning Education and Research* 22(4): 360-373.

Lee, M. & Rubin, V., 2006. "The impact of the built environment on community health: The state of current practice and next steps for a growing movement". Produced by PolicyLink for the California Endowment. Available at http://www.calendow.org/uploadedfiles/the_built_environment_report.pdf

Lithgow, S; Jackson, G.; & Browne, D., 2012. "Estimating the prevalence of dementia; cognitive screening in Glasgow nursing homes". *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 27, 785-791.

Luenngo-Fernandez, R., Leal, J. & Gray, A., 2010. *Dementia 2010: The Economic Burden of Dementia and Associated Research Funding in the United Kingdom*, Alzheimer's Research Trust, London.

Marmot, M., Siegrist, J. & Theorell, T., 2005. "Health and the psycho-social environment at work". In Marmot, M. and Wilkinson, R. (eds), *Social Determinants of Health*. Oxford, University Press, New York, pp. 105-27.

Mitchell, L. & Burton, E., 2006. "Neighbourhoods for life: designing dementia-friendly outside environments". *Quality in Ageing*, 7(1), 26-33.

Murphy, J., Tester, S., Hubbard, G., Downs, M. & MacDonald, C., 2005. "Enabling frail older people with a communication difficulty to express their views: the use of Talking Mats™ as an inter view tool". *Health and Social Care in the Community*, 13(2), 95-107.

Northern Ireland Government, 2011. *Improving Dementia Services in Northern Ireland – a Regional Strategy* available at <http://www.dhsspsni.gov.uk/show-publications?btxid=53089>

Peréz, E (2014) *Integrationsarbetets villkor och paradoxer*. In Lalander, P och Svensson, B *Social utsatthet i perspektiv*. Studentlitteratur.

Pol, Enric. *Impacte social, comunicació ambiental i participació*. Barcelona: Generalitat de Catalunya. Departament de Medi Ambient. 2000

Raco, M. (2000). *Assessing Community Participation in Local Economic Development: Lessons for the New Urban Policy*. *Political Geography* 19: 573-599.

Sanoff, Henry. *Programación y participación en el diseño arquitectónico*. Barcelona: Ediciones UPC, 2006

Sarkissian, W., D. Hurford & C. Wenman (2010). *Creative Community Planning: Transformative Engagemet Methods for Working at the Edge*. Earthscan

Scott, P. A., Valimaki, M., Leino-Kilpi, H., Dassen, T., Gasull, M., Lemonidou, C. & Arndt, M., 2003. "Autonomy, privacy and informed consent. 3: Elderly care perspective". *British Journal of Nursing*, 12(2), 158-68.

Scottish Government, 2010. *Scotland's National Dementia Strategy* available at <http://www.scotland.gov.uk/Publications/2010/09/10151751/0>

Seeger, K.M., 2012. *Dropout prediction for an early intervention for sub-threshold and mild panic disorder*. University of Twente, p. 7.

Spiriduso, W.W.; Cronin, D.L., 2001. "Exercise dose-response effects on quality of life and independent living in older adults". *Med Sci Sports Exerc.*, 33(6) (suppl), 598-608.

Srinivasan, S.; O'Fallon, L.R. & Dearry, A., 2003. "Creating healthy communities, healthy homes, healthy people: Initiating a research agenda on the built environment and public health". *American Journal of Public Health*, 93(9), 1446-1450.

Tett, L. (2005) *Partnerships, Community Groups and Social Inclusion*. *Studies in Continuing Education* 27(1): 1-15.

Torrington, J., 2009. "Extra care housing: environmental design to support activity and meaningful engagement for people with dementia". *Journal of Care Services Management*, 3(3), 250-257.

Van Loan, M.D., 2007, "Do Hand-Held Calorimeters Provide Reliable and Accurate Estimates of Resting Metabolic Rate?" *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 26(6), 625-629.

7.6 Urban climate

Vidrih, B., in Medved, S. The effects of changes in the climate on the energy demands of buildings. *International Journal of Energy Research*, 2008, 32 (11): 1016–1029.

Day, A. R., Jones, P. G., in Maidment, G. G. Forecasting future cooling demand in London. *Energy and Buildings*, 2009, 41 (9): 942–948.

The EU climate and energy package. Dostopno na http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/package/index_en.htm (22. 4. 2013).

Wong, N. H., s sod. Thermal evaluation of vertical greenery systems for building walls. *Building and Environment* 2010, 45: 663–672.

Knaack, U. *Facades – Principles of Construction*. Birkhauser Verlag AG, Berlin, Nemčija, 2007.

Loonen, R. *Climate adaptive building shells: What can we simulate?* Magistrsko delo. Technische Universiteit Eindhoven. Eindhoven, Nizozemska, 2010.

Philips Design Probes. *Offthe Grid: Sustainable Habitat 2020*. Dostopno na http://www.design.philips.com/philips/sites/philipsdesign/about/design/designportfolio/design_futures/design_probes/projects/sustainable_habitat_2020.page (31. 2. 2011).

Vidrih, B. Vpliv globalnih podnebnih sprememb in urbanizacije na lokalne klimatske razmere v mestih. Doktorsko delo. Fakulteta za strojništvo, Univerza v Ljubljani, Ljubljana, 2011.

Vidrih, B., in Medved, S. Multiparametric model of urban park cooling island. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 2013, 12 (2): 220–229.

Nachtigall, W. *Bau-bionik*. Springer, Berlin, Nemčija, 2003.

Senosiain, J. *Bio-Architecture*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, Nizozemska, 2003.

Braun, D. H. *Bionischinspirierte Gebäudehüllen*. Doktorsko delo. Fakultät Architektur und Stadtplanung, Universität Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Nemčija, 2008.

Badarnah, L. *Towards the living envelope: Biomimetics for building envelope adaptation*. Doktorsko delo. Technische Universiteit Delft, Delft, Nizozemska, 2012.

Pérez, G., s sod. Green vertical systems for buildings as passive systems for energy savings. *Applied Energy*, 2011, 88: 4854–4859.

Perini, K., s sod. Vertical greening systems, a processtree for green façades and livingwalls. *Urban Ecosystems*, 2012: 1–13.

Sheweka, S. M., in Mohamed, N. M. Green Facades as a New Sustainable Approach Towards Climate Change. *Energy Procedia*, 2012, 18 (0): 507–520.

Köhler, M. *Greenfacades – a view back and some visions*. *Urban Ecosystems*, 2008, 11 (4): 423–436.

Perini, K., s sod. Vertical greening systems and the effect on airflow and temperature on the building envelope. *Building and Environment*, 2011, 46: 2287–2294.

Ottelé, M. *The Green Building Envelope: Vertical Greening*. Doktorsko delo. Materials & Environmentchair Sustainability, Civil Engineering and Geosciences, Technische Universiteit Delft, Delft, Nizozemska, 2011.

Pérez, G., s sod. Behaviour of green facades in Mediterranean Continental climate. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 2011, 52 (4): 1861–1867.

Stec, W. J., van Paassen, A. H. C., in Maziarz, A. Modelling the double skin façade with plants. *Energy and Buildings*, 2005, 37 (5): 419–427.

Ottelé, M., s sod. Comparative lifecycle analysis for green façades and livingwall systems. *Energy and Buildings*, 2011, 43 (12): 3419–3429.

Fang, W., s sod. The thermal performance of double skin façade with Till and saiusneoides plantcurtain. *Energy and Buildings*, 2011, 43 (9): 2127–2133.

Stanghellini, C. Mixed convection above greenhouse cropcanopies. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 1993, 66 (1–2): 111–117.

Jim, C. Y., in He, H. Estimating heat fluxtransmission of vertical greenery ecosystem. *Ecological Engineering*, 2011, 37 (8): 1112–1122.

Černe, B. Vpliv večdimenzijskega prenosa toplote na toplotni odziv lahkih gradbenih elementov. Doktorsko delo. Fakulteta za strojništvo, Univerza v Ljubljani, Ljubljana, 2006.

Machado, M. V., s sod. Sol air temperature in the ecological roof. *Proceedings of Plea*, Cambridge, 2000.

Wong, N. H., s sod. Energy simulation of vertical greenery systems. *Energy and Buildings*, 2009, 41: 1401–1408.

Johnston, J., in Newton, J. *Building Green: A guide to using plants on roofs, walls and pavements*. Greater London Authority, London, 2004.

Gosztonyi, S. *Bionische Fassaden: BioSkin – Forschungspotenziale aus der Bionik für adaptive energie effiziente Fassaden der Zukunft*, 2011. Dostopno na http://www.oegut.at/downloads/pdf/Gosztonyi_AIT_BioSKin_S_310311.pdf (25. 9. 2012).

Ritter, A. *Smart materials in architecture, interior architecture and design*. Birkhauser, Berlin, Nemčija, 2007.

He, J., in Hoyano, A. A numerical simulation method for analyzing the thermal improvement effect of super-hydrophilicphotocatalyst-coated buildingsurfaces with water film on the urban/built environment. *Energy and Buildings*, 2008, 40 (6): 968–978.

Naticchia, B., s sod. Energy performance evaluation of a novel evaporative cooling technique. *Energy and Buildings*, 2010, 42: 1926–1938.

Varga, S., Oliveira, A. C., in Afonso, C. F. Characterisation of thermal diode panels for use in the cooling season in buildings. *Energy and Buildings*, 2002, 34 (3): 227–235.

Chen, K., s sod. The dynamic behavior of a bayonet-type thermal diode. *Solar Energy*, 1998, 64 (4-6): 257–263.

Chan, A. L. S., s sod. Investigation on energy performance of double skin façade in HongKong. *Energy and Buildings*, 2009, 41 (11): 1135–1142.

Eicker, U., s sod. *Façades and summer performance of buildings*. *Energy and Buildings*, 2008, 40 (4): 600–611.

Gratia, E., in De Herde, A. Natural cooling strategies efficiency in an office building with a double-skin façade. *Energy and Buildings*, 2004, 36 (11): 1139–52.

Stec, W. J., in Paassen, A. H. Defining the performance of the double skin facade with the use of the simulation model. *Eighth International IBPSA Conference*, 2003.

Park, C. S., s sod. Calibration of a lumped simulation model for double-skin façade systems. *Energy and Buildings*, 2004, 36 (11): 1117–1130.

Kuznik, F., s sod. Numerical modelling of combined heat transfers in a double skin façade – Full-scale laboratory experiment validation. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 2011, 31 (14–15): 3043–3054.

Palyvos, J. A. A survey of wind convection coefficient correlations for building envelope energy systems' modeling. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 2008, 28 (8–9): 801–808.

Zanghirella, F., Perino, M., in Serra, V. A numerical model to evaluate the thermal behaviour of active transparent façades. *Energy and Buildings*, 2011, 43 (5): 1123–1138.

Jiru, T. E., in Haghighat, F. Modeling ventilated doubleskin façade – A zonal approach. *Energy and Buildings*, 2008, 40 (8): 1567–1576.

Laouadi, A. Thermal modeling of shading devices of windows. *ASHRAE Transactions*, 2009, 115 (2): 1–20.

Safer, N., Woloszyn, M., in Roux, J. J. Three-dimensional simulation with a CFD tool of the airflow phenomena in singlefloor double-skin facade equipped with a venetian blind. *Solar Energy*, 2005, 79 (2): 193–203.

Manz, H., Schaelein, A., in Simmler, H. Airflow patterns and thermal behavior of mechanically ventilated glass double façades. *Building and Environment*, 2004, 39 (9): 1023–1033.

Saneinejad, S., s sod. Coupled CFD, radiation and porousmedia transport model for evaluating evaporative cooling in an urban environment. <i>Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics</i> , 2012, 104–106 (0): 455–463.
Defraeye, T., Blocken, B., in Carmeliet, J. Convective heat transfer coefficients for exterior building surfaces: Existing correlations and CFD modelling. <i>Energy Conversion and Management</i> , 2011, 52 (1): 512–522.
Sanjuan, C., s sod. Energy performance of an open-joint ventilated façade compared with a conventional sealed cavity façade. <i>Solar Energy</i> , 2011, 85 (9): 1851–1863.
Pasut, W., in De Carli, M. Evaluation of various CFD modelling strategies in predicting airflow and temperature in a naturally ventilated double skin façade. <i>Applied Thermal Engineering</i> , 2012, 37 (0): 267–274.
Gebhart, B. <i>Heat Transfer</i> . McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, ZDA, 1961.
Saneinejad, S., s sod. Analysis of convective heat and mass transfer at the vertical walls of a street canyon. <i>Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics</i> , 2011, 99 (4): 424–433.
Yang, X., s sod. An integrated simulation method for building energy performance assessment in urban environments. <i>Energy and Buildings</i> , 2012, 54 (0): 243–251.
Bruse, M. ENVI-met 2011. Dostopno na http://www.envi-met.com/ (28. 2. 2013).
Giancola, E., s sod. Experimental assessment and modelling of the performance of an open joint ventilated façade during actual operating conditions in Mediterranean climate. <i>Energy and Buildings</i> , 2012, 54 (0): 363–375.
Fang, X., in Xia, L. Heating performance investigation of a bidirectional partition fluidthermal diode. <i>Renewable Energy</i> , 2010, 35 (3): 679–684.
Perino, M., in Serra, V. Transparent active facade: results from a year round field monitoring, 2003. Dostopno na http://www.europeangreencities.com/pdf/activities/ConfApr2004/14.pdf (15. 4. 2013).
Tingqiao, Y., in Xiufang, K. Study on Thermal Performance of Passive Evaporative Cooling Double-Skin Facade, 2011. <i>International Conference on Measuring Technology and Mechatronics Automation (ICMTMA)</i> . Šanghaj, 2011.
Qahtan, A., s sod. Experimental determination of thermal performance of glazed façades with water film, under direct solar radiation in the tropics. <i>Building and Environment</i> , 2011, 46 (11): 2238–2246.
Stec, W. J., Paassen, A. H., in Maziarz, A. Modelling the double skin façade with plants. <i>Energy and Buildings</i> , 2005, 37: 419–427.
Serra, V., Zanghirella, F., in Perino, M. Experimental evaluation of a climate façade: Energy efficiency and thermal comfort performance. <i>Energy and Buildings</i> , 2010, 42 (1): 50–62.
Chen, W. Thermal analysis on the cooling performance of a wet porousevaporative plate for building. <i>Energy Conversion and Management</i> , 2011, 52 (5): 2217–2226.
SIST EN ISO 13786, Thermal performance of building components – Dynamic thermal characteristics – Calculation methods. European committee for standardization, Bruselj, Belgija, 2008.
Medved, S., in Šuklje, T. KI Energija 2010: izračun rabe energije v stavbah. <i>Energetska učinkovitost in energetska izkaznica stavb</i> , 2011.
Šuklje, T. Računalniško orodje za vrednotenje energetskih kazalnikov stavb. Diplomsko delo. Fakulteta za strojništvo, Univerza v Ljubljani, Ljubljana, 2011.

Kastner-Klein P., Plate E.J. 1999. Wind-tunnel study of concentration fields in street canyons. *Atmospheric Environment* 33 (24): 3973-3979.

Kent S.T., Howard G., Crosson W.L., Prineas R.J., McClure L.A. 2011. The association of remotely sensed outdoor temperature with blood pressure levels in REGARDS: a cross-sectional study of a large, national cohort of African-American and white participants. *Environmental Health*, 10 (7): 1-12.

Kinney P.L., 2008. Climate Change, Air Quality, and Human Health. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 35(5): 459-467.

Kjelgren R., Montague T. 1998. Urban tree transpiration over turf and asphalt surfaces. *Atmospheric Environment* 32:35-41.

Kolokotroni M., Giridharan R. 2008. Urban heat island intensity in London: an investigation of the impact of physical characteristics on changes in outdoor air temperature during summer. *Solar Energy*, 82(11):986-998.

Kovats R.S., Hajat S. 2008. Heat stress and public health: a critical review. *Annual Review of Public Health*, 29:41-55.

Kovats S., Elbi K.L., Menne B. 2003. Health and Global Environmental Change. Series No.1: Methods of Assessing Human Health Vulnerability and Public Health Adaptation to Climate Change. World Health Organization. Copenhagen, 112 str.

Krüger E.L., Minella F.O., Rasia F. 2011. Impact of urban geometry on outdoor thermal comfort and air quality field measurements in Curitiba, Brazil. *Building and Environment* 46:621-634.

Kumar R., Kaushik S.C. 2005. Performance evaluation of green roof and shading for thermal protection of buildings. *Building and Environment*, 40:1505-1511.

Li J.F., Wai O.W.H., Li Y.S., Zhan J.M., Ho Y.A., Li J., Lam E. 2010. Effects of green roof on ambient CO2 concentration. *Building and Environment*, 45: 2644-2651.

Lugo-Amador N., Rotenhaus T., Moyer P. 2004. Heat-related illness. *Emergency Medicine Clinics of North America*, 22:315-327.

Macdonald R.W. 2000. Modelling the mean velocity profile in the urban canopy layer. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology* 97:25-45.

Masterdon J.M., Richardson F.A. 2009. Humidex: A Method of Quantifying Human Discomfort due to Excessive Heat and Humidity, Environment Canada, Atmospheric Environment Service, Ontario, Canada.

Matsumoto M., Ishikawa S., Kajii E. 2010. Cumulative effects of weather on stroke incidence: A multi community cohort study in Japan. *Journal of Epidemiology*, 20(2): 136-142.

McMichael A.J. 2008. International study of temperature, heat and urban mortality: the 'ISOTHURM' project. *International Journal of Epidemiology* 37(5):1121-31.

Medved S. 2010. Gradbena fizika. Univerza v Ljubljani. Fakulteta za arhitekturo. 320 str.

Mensink C., Lewyckij, N. 2001. A simple model for the assessment of air quality in streets. *International Journal of Vehicle Design*, 27 (1): 242-250.

Mills G.M. 1993. Simulation of the energy budget of an urban canyon – I. Model structure and sensitivity test. *Atmospheric Environment. Part B. Urban Atmosphere* 27(2):157-170.

Mirzaei P.A. Haghighat F. 2010. Approaches to study Urban Heat Island-Abilities and limitations. *Building and Environment*, 45: 2192-2201.

Naughton M.P., Henderson A., Mirabelli M.C., Kaiser R., Wilhelm J.L., Stephanie M., Kieszak M., Rubin C.H., McGeehin A. 2002. Heat-related mortality during a 1999 heat wave in Chicago. *American journal of preventive medicine*, 22(4):221-227.

Neofytou P., Venetsanos A., Bartzis J.G. 2006. Wind-field and pollution dispersion simulation in a street canyon in Helsinki with ADREA-HF code. *Global NEST Journal*, 8 (3): 272-276.

Ng E., Chen L., Wang Y., Yuan C. 2012. A study on the cooling effects of greening in a high-density city: An experience from Hong Kong. *Building and Environment* 47: 256-271.

Niachou K., Livada I., Santamouris M. 2008. Experimental study of temperature and air flow distribution inside an urban street canyon during hot summer weather conditions. Part II: Airflow analysis. *Building and Environment* 43:1393-1403.

Nowak D.J., Crane D.E., Stevens J.C. 2006. Air pollution removal by urban trees and shrubs in the United States. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 4:115-123.

Oke T.R. 1982. Overview of interactions between settlements and their environments. WMO experts meeting on urban and building climatology WCP-37, WMO Geneva.

Olesen B.W. 2004. International standards for indoor environment. *Indoor Air*. 14(7):18-26.

Onishi A., Cao X., Ito T., Shi F., Imura H. 2010. Evaluating the potential for urban heat-island mitigation by greening parking lots. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 9: 323-332.

Páldy A., Bobvos J. Vámos A., Kovats R.S., Hajat. 2005. The effect of Temperature and Heat Waves on Daily Mortality in Budapest, Hungary, 1970-2000. V: Kirch W., Monne B., Bertolini R. (ur). *Extreme Weather Events and Public Health Responses*. Springer. Berlin Heidelberg New York. 69-80.

Parsons K.C. 2003. Human thermal environment. The effects of hot, moderate, and cold environments on human health, comfort and performance. CRC Press, London. 518 str.

Peters A., Perz S., Döring A., Stieber J., Joenig W., Wichmann H.E. 1999. Increases in heart rate during air pollution episode. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 150 (10):1094-1098.

Plavcová E., Kyselý J. 2010. Relationship between sudden weather changes in summer and mortality in the Czech Republic, 1986-2005. *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 54: 539-551.

Pope C.A III, Verrier R.L., Lovett E.G., Larson A.C., Raizenne M.E., Kanner R.E. 1999. Heart rate variability associated with particulate air pollution. *American Heart Journal*, 138:890-899.

Potcher O., Cohen P., Bitan A. 2006. Climatic behaviour of various urban parks during hot and humid summer Mediterranean city of Tel Aviv, Israel. *International Journal of Climatology* 26:1695-1711.

Rainham D.G.C., Smoyer-Tomic K.E. 2003. The role of air pollution in the relationship between a heat stress index and human mortality in Toronto. *Environmental Research*, 93(1):9-19.

Rey G., Jouglé E., Fouillet A. Pavillon G., Bassemoulin P., Frayssinet P., Clavel J., Hémond D. 2007. The impact of major heat waves on all-cause and cause-specific mortality in France from 1971 to 2003. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 80:615-626.

Sakakibara Y. 1996. A numerical study of the effect of urban geometry upon the surface energy budget. *Atmospheric Environment* 30 (3):487-496.

Sanesi G., Gallis C., Kasperidus H.D. 2011. Urban forest and their ecosystem services in relation to human health. V: Nilsson K., Sangster M., Gallis C., Harting T., de Vries S., Seeland K., Schipperijn J. *Forest, trees and human health*. Springer Science+Business Media 23-40.

Santamouris M. 2001. Energy and climate in the urban built environment. James&James Ltd, London, UK.

Santamouris M., Pavlou C., Doukas P., Mihalakakou G., Synnefa A., Hatzibiros A., Patargias P. 2007. Investigating and analysing the energy and environmental performance of an experimental green roof system installed in a nursery school building in Athens, Greece. *Energy*, 32:1781-1788.

Sarkovich M. 2002. SMUD's Urban Heat Island Mitigation Efforts. Special Panel on Heat Island Mitigation. American Council for Energy Efficient Economy, Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Buildings, Pacific Grove, PA, Sacramento Municipal Utility District.

Schipperijn J., Stigsdotter U.K., Randrup T.B., Troelsen J. 2010. Influence on the use of urban green space – A case study in Odense, Denmark. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 9:25-32.

Shashua-Bar L., Hoffman M.E. Tzamiir Y. 2006. Integrated thermal effects of generic built forms and vegetation on the UCL microclimate. *Building and Environment* 41:343-354.

Shashua-Bar L., Pearlmutter D., Erell E. 2011. The influence of trees and grass on outdoor thermal comfort in a hot-arid environment. *International Journal of Climatology* 31:1498-1506.

Silva R.H., Phelan P.E., Golden J.S. 2010. Modeling effects of urban heat island mitigation strategies on heat-related morbidity: a case study for Phoenix, Arizona. *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 54:13-22.

SIST CR 1752 :1999. Prezračevanje stavb–Kriteriji načrtovanja notranjega okolja. 80 str.

7.7 Cooling and heating

Baviskar, A. 2003, Between violence and desire: space, power, and identity in the making of metropolitan Delhi. <i>International Social Science Journal</i> , Vol. 55, Issue 175, pp. 89-98.	
Baviskar, A. 2013, Particopolis: protest and participation in the city, pp. 306-308. In: Coelho, K., Kamath, L., & Vijayabaskar, M. 2013, <i>Particopolis, consent and contention in Neoliberal urban India</i> . Routledge, New Delhi.	
Banerjee-Guha, S. 2009, Neoliberalising the 'urban': new geographies of power and injustice in Indian Cities. <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , Vol. XLIV, no. 22, pp. 95-107.	
Beall, J and Piron , H. 2005, "DFID Social Exclusion Review", London, London School of Economics/Overseas Development Institute	
Birkinshaw, M., Harris, V. The right to the "world class city"? City visions and evictions in Mumbai. 2005-2009, <i>The Urban Reinventors</i> . www.urbanreinventors.net [accessed 3 Feb 2014].	
Bhan, G. 2009, "This is no longer the city I once knew". Evictions, the urban poor and the right to the city in millennium Delhi. <i>Environment and Urbanization</i> , 2009, vol. 21(1): pp.127-142.	no. 13 2723-
Bhide, A. 2009, Shifting terrains of communities and community organization: reflections on organizing for housing rights in Mumbai. <i>Community Development Journal</i> , vol.44, no.3, pp.367-381.	
Cerneia, M. M. 2009, Financing for development. Benefit-sharing mechanisms in population resettlement, pp. 49-77. In: Oliver-Smith, A., <i>Development and dispossession, the crisis of forced displacement and resettlement</i> . School of Advanced Research Press, Santa Fe, New Mexico.	
COHRE, 2006, Forced evictions, violations of human rights. Global survey on forced evictions No. 10. Centre on Housing Rights and Evictions, Geneva, Switzerland.	
Coelho, K., Venkat, T., & Chandrika, R. 2012, The spatial reproduction of urban poverty. In: <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , Vol. 47, Nr 47 & 48.	
Coelho, K., Venkat, T., & Chandrika, R. 2013, Housing, homes and domestic work, a study of paid domestic workers from a resettlement colony in Chennai. <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , No.43, pp.39-46.	
Cornwall, A. 2008, Unpacking 'participation': models, meaning and practices. <i>Community Development Journal</i> , Vol. 43, No. 3, pp. 269-283.	
Courtland Robinson, W., 2003, Risks and rights: the causes, consequences, and challenges of development-induced displacement, an occasional paper. The Brookings Institution – SAIS Project on Internal Displacement, May 2003.	
Datta, A. 2012, 'The illegal city, space, law and gender in a Delhi settlement', Surrey: Ashgate Publishing Limited.	
De Haan, L. & Zoomers, A. 2005, 'Exploring the frontier of livelihood research' in: <i>Development and Change</i> , Vol. 36, Issue 1.	
Dupont, V. 2011a, The challenge of slums and forced evictions, pp. 76-97. In: <i>Urban policies and the right to the city in India, rights, responsibilities and citizenship</i> . UNESCO, New Delhi.	
Dupont, V. 2011, The dream of Delhi as a global city. <i>International Journal of Urban and Regional Research</i> , Vol. 35.3, May 2011, pp.533-545.	
Dupont, V., Danalaksmi, R. 2013, Chennai, India, in: <i>Addressing sub-standard settlements. Wp3 Settlement Fieldwork Report</i> , coordinated by Braathen, E. <i>Chance2Sustain</i> .	
Ellis, R. 2013, Public performances: enacting citizenship through public consultation for Chennai's second Masterplan (pp.256-275). In: Coelho, K., Kamath, L., & Vijayabaskar, M. 2013, <i>Particopolis, consent and contention in Neoliberal urban India</i> . Routledge, New Delhi.	
Ellis, R. 2012, A world class city of your own! Civic governmentability in Chennai, India. <i>Antipode</i> , Vol. 44, No.4, pp. 1143-1160.	
Gore, C. 2000, The rise and fall of the Washington Consensus as a paradigm for developing countries. <i>World Development</i> , Vol. 28, No. 5, pp. 789-804.	
Hasan, A. 2010, The world class city concept and its repercussions on urban planning for cities in the Asia pacific region, pp. 287-299. In: Sugranyes, A., Mathivet, Y., <i>Cities for all: experiences and proposals for the right to the city</i> . HIC, Santiago.	
Kundu, A. 2013, Making Indian cities slum-free, vision and operationalization. <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , Vol 48, No. 17.	
Langford, M., and J. du Plessis, 2004, Dignity in the rubble? Forced evictions and human rights law. COHRE, Geneva, Switzerland.	
Mahadevia, D. 2006. NJRM and the poor in globalizing mega cities. <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , Vol. 41, No. 31, pp.3399-3403.	
Mehta, L., (ed). 2009, <i>Displaced by development, confronting marginalization and gender injustice</i> . Sage Publications, New Delhi.	
Mathur, O.P. 2009, <i>National Urban Poverty reduction strategy 2010-2020, Slum free cities</i> . The National Institute of Public Finance and Policy (NIPFP), July 2009.	
Nandi, S., Gamskar, S. 2013, Urban challenges in India: a review of recent policy measures. <i>Habitat International</i> , Vol.39, pp.55-61.	
Nijdam, J. 2008, Against the odds: slum rehabilitation in neoliberal Mumbai. <i>Cities</i> , Vol. 25, pp. 73-85.	
Pender, J. 2001, From 'structural adjustment' to 'comprehensive development framework': conditionality transformed? <i>Third World Quarterly</i> , Vol. 22, No. 3, pp. 397 - 411.	
Rakodi, C. 2002, 'A Livelihoods Approach – Conceptual Issues and Definitions' In: C. Rakodi and T. Lloyd Jones: <i>Urban Livelihoods: A people centered approach to Urban Poverty</i> . Earthscan Publications.	nr - 1.
Raman, N.V. 2011, The Board and the Bank: changing policies towards slums in Chennai. <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , No. 31, pp. 74-80.	
Raman, N.V. 2013, The messy practice of participation: lessons from the City development plan (CDP) review in Chennai (pp.276-297). In: Coelho, K., Kamath, L., & Vijayabaskar, M. 2013, <i>Particopolis, consent and contention in Neoliberal urban India</i> . Routledge, New Delhi.	
Rao, U. 2013, Tolerated encroachment: resettlement policies and the negotiation of the licit/illicit divide in an Indian metropolis. <i>Cultural Anthropology</i> , Vol. 28, Issue 4, pp.760-779.	
Roy, A. 2011, The blockage of the world-class city: dialectical images of Indian urbanism, chapter 10, pp. 259-278. In: Roy, A., Ong, A (eds.). <i>Worlding cities, Asian experiments and the art of being global</i> . Wiley, Blackwell, UK.	
Vijayabaskar, M., Coelho, K., Venkat, T., Sekhar, S., Pathak, M., Toshnival R. July 2011, Status report on urban reform in Tamil Nadu (SRUR).	2723-2733.
Dwivedi, R. 2002, Models and methods in development-induced displacement (review article). <i>Development and Change</i> , Vol. 33, No.4, pp. 709-732.	
Ruet, J., Tawa Lama-Reval, S. 2009. <i>Governing India's metropolises</i> . Routledge: New Delhi.	
Cerneia, M. 1988, Involuntary resettlement in development projects: policy guidelines in World Bank financed projects. Washington D.C., World Bank.	
Cerneia, M.M. 2000, Risks, safeguards and reconstruction, a model for population displacement and resettlement. <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , XXXV, 41, pp. 3659-3678.	
Muggah, R. 2008, Relocation failures in Sri Lanka, a short history of internal displacement and resettlement. London, Zed Books	
de Wet, C. 2001, Economic development and population displacement, can everybody win? <i>Economic and Political Weekly</i> , pp. 4637-4646, Dec 15, 2001.	
Levien, M., 2011, The land question: special economic zones and the political economy of dispossession in India. Paper presented at the International Conference on Global Land Grabbing, 6-8 April 201, Institute of Development Studies, University of Sussex.	
Mehta, L. 2011, The settler and his wife, gender and the politics of displacement, pp. 25-43. DEP, No. 17.	
Viratkapan, V., Perera, R. 2006, Slum relocation projects in Bangkok: what has contributed to their success or failure? <i>Habitat International</i> , Vol. 30, pp. 157-174.	
Oliver-Smith, A., 2010, <i>Defying displacement, grassroots resistance and the critique of development</i> . University of Texas Press, Austin, Texas.	
J. D. Spitzer, C.O. Pedersen, D.E. Fisher, P.F. Menne, J. Cantillo, Interior convective heat transfer in buildings with large ventilative flow rates, <i>ASHRAE Transactions</i> 97 (1) (1991) 505-515.	
http://www.trnsys.com/	

7.8 Waterfront

Mrđenović, http://issuu.com/iipp/docs/2_2011_9

Books

Urban regeneration of protected ambients in the context of sustainable development – Bač Fortress Suburbium, author: Tatjana Mrđenović; group of authors: Jelica Jovanović, Mila Pucar, Ana Radivojević, Slavica Vujović, Dragana Petrović, Dragana Marjanović, publisher University of Belgrade – Faculty of Architecture, 2011, financed by Ministry of education and science, Republic of Serbia <http://obavezni.digital.nb.rs/izdavac/af/publikacija/11>

Books chapters

Urban regeneration and integrative urban design: Challenges for Serbian legislative framework/ Urbana regeneracija i integrativni urbani dizajn: Izazovi za srpski zakonodavni okvir, (2012) author: Tatjana Mrđenović In. Climate Change and the Built Environment: Policies and Practice in Scotland and Serbia / Klimatske promene i građena sredina: Politike i praksa u Škotskoj i Srbiji, ed. Mila Pucar, Branka Dimitrijević, Igor Marić

Urban regeneration and integrative urban design: Challenges for Serbian teaching practice / Urbana regeneracija i integrativni urbani dizajn: Izazovi za edukacione procese u Srbiji, (2012) author: Tatjana Mrđenović In. Climate Change and the Built Environment: Policies and Practice in Scotland and Serbia / Klimatske promene i građena sredina: Politike i praksa u Škotskoj i Srbiji, ed. Mila Pucar, Branka Dimitrijević, Igor Marić ,